

**TOWARDS
A NATIONAL
COLLECTION**

**UK
RI**

**Arts and
Humanities
Research Council**

COMMISSIONED REPORT

**TaNC Impact Evaluation:
Final Report**

February 2025

Diffley Partnership

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Executive Summary

TaNC Programme

Towards a National Collection (TaNC) was awarded £18.9 million within the digital theme of the UK Research and Innovation's (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF). TaNC is delivered by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and supported by the UK government's Department for Culture Media and Sport (DCMS) and AHRC's independent research organisations.¹

The objectives of TaNC were to:

- Begin to dissolve barriers between different collections.
- Open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research.
- Extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location.
- Benefit a diverse range of audiences.
- Be active and of benefit across the UK.
- Provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward.²

TaNC's competitive funding calls resulted in:

- Eight small-scale Foundation Projects began in February 2020 and all were completed by July 2022.
- Three COVID-19 Projects, with the first beginning in January 2021 and all were completed by March 2022.
- Five major Discovery Projects began in October 2021 and all were completed by January 2025.

Evaluation

The evaluation included analysis of secondary sources (see Appendix B). Primary research was also designed and conducted to generate rich insights from participants in TaNC's projects (see Appendix C). GLAM sector surveys were conducted at two time points to gather information including awareness of TaNC, importance of TaNC's objectives and opinions on performance of TaNC (see Appendix F).

The Interim Evaluation Report was previously published by the TaNC Programme Directorate in August 2023.³ Evaluation engagement then recommenced in August 2024. Evaluators looked at additional sources, including final reports by Discovery Projects. They also conducted six further evaluation engagement sessions and attended TaNC's final conference.

The evaluation culminates in this final Impact evaluation report.

¹ [Strategic Priorities Fund – UKRI](#)

² [Towards a National Collection - Research and scholarship \(nationalarchives.gov.uk\)](#)

³ [Impact Evaluation Interim Report \(Towards a National Collection\)](#)

Findings- impacts for cultural heritage organisations

GLAM survey 2 respondents involved in TaNC projects were most positive that TaNC:

- Helped us develop collaborations with other organisations.
- Helped us improve working across different disciplines.
- Helped us to be innovative.
- Helped us engage with public audiences.
- Helped us develop partnerships with the higher education sector.

Views were more mixed that TaNC:

- Helped skills development in our organisation.

And were more negative that TaNC:

- Helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy.
- Helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability.
- Helped us improve digital search of collections records.

There was an expectation that TaNC's Programme Directorate would be advancing discussions at higher policy levels which may lead to benefits for the GLAM sector.

For organisations heavily involved in TaNC, there was evidence that digital policy and strategy was improved. Certainly, TaNC Discovery Projects provided opportunities for IROs to explore, discuss and update some of their policies and procedures. Also, for those funded through TaNC projects, that digital capacity and capability were improved for the project durations.

However, there is currently no evidence that TaNC directly improved the digital policies and strategies or the digital capacity and capability of the other GLAM partner organisations in Discovery Projects. There was also

concern expressed throughout the evaluation that TaNC may not have had significant impact on smaller, non-national GLAM organisations.

Having said that, many evaluation materials explained the challenges facing the GLAM sector regarding long-standing limitations with digital policies, workforce skills and funding levels. Although hopeful that TaNC would lead to transformational change benefitting the whole sector, this is seen as more achievable following the end of Discovery Projects as part of legacy from 2025 and onwards.

Findings- impacts for collections and their audiences

The audit TaNC commissioned from the Collections Trust provided evidence of some of the barriers to dissolving barriers between collections.⁴ These were echoed by evaluation participants. Furthermore, the Discovery Projects brought knowledge and understanding of constraints of existing metadata.

Discovery Projects have helped establish what is not only theoretically possible, but what is practically possible. Discovery Project final reports, and their technical recommendations set these out. For example, 'Collections Linkage' was put forward as an alternative to attempting to create 'a national collection'.

Furthermore, Discovery Projects make a meaningful contribution to considerations of what collections should and can be included, such as existing records held by GLAMs and community-generated content.

Evaluation participants encouraged others to consider what potential users would find most valuable, rather than stick to their own presumptions. Helpfully, the Audience Agency, working in collaboration with Culture 24, was commissioned by TaNC to 'deliver user research to understand what users want and need from a future national collection digital infrastructure.' These findings add value to the understanding of the behaviours of members of the public engaging with digital content by GLAMs.⁵

TaNC projects have included public programming, user research and co-design which could be taken as evidence that TaNC benefitted audiences.

Similarly, TaNC projects individually should lead to digital initiatives which are designed to benefit audiences.

All the same, the question remains as to how diverse these audience are, and with respect to which criteria, such as by demographic categorisations or area of residence. From desk materials and evaluation sessions it is clear that people involved in TaNC are conscious, and in some cases very proactive, to ensure diversity and inclusion is at the forefront of digital developments in GLAM.

The evaluation found that different disciplinary perspectives were brought into the overall TaNC programme, and TaNC at project-level. In terms of digital developments resulting through TaNC, many of these were developed to bring together collections collected by different disciplines and many were developed with end users from different disciplines, or interests in mind.

⁴ Gosling, Kevin, McKenna, Gordon, & Cooper, Adrian. (2022). Digital Collections Audit. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379581>

⁵ Woodley, Sophia, & Towell, Patrick. (2022). User Research. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

Findings- impacts of digital collections research ecosystem

In terms of TaNC benefits reaching across the UK, this was evidenced by the number of organisations based in different UK locations. Due to the set up with IROs and HEIs these were consequently based in large population centres. There were clearly efforts to include organisations, and people, based in as many parts of the UK as possible.

Collaboration across geographies, types and sizes of organisations was described as valuable but challenging. Evaluation participants reflected that having large numbers of partners may look good on paper, but in practice it takes resource to ensure all are involved meaningfully in a project.

Certainly, learnings from TaNC were seen as useful to inform a shared vision for a national collection and deciding on future priorities and practical next steps (see chapter 8 for future priorities). There was a sense of a growing community given TaNC had brought skills, resource and capacity into HEIs and IROs in particular. Parity for the wider GLAM sector was seen as important, by HEIs and IROs, this was based upon their observations that some wider project partners brought more towards TaNC projects than they gained in the short-term.

Another objective of TaNC was to advance the case for enhanced funding. TaNC has resulted in many examples to build upon. An important factor for success is the strong motivation, and work of all TaNC projects to share their findings.⁶ Discovery Projects produced prolific outputs for different audiences such as websites, films, articles, case studies and reports. Furthermore, TaNC can leverage commissioned reports such as the Total Economic Value of a Unified Digital Collection.⁷

Findings- evaluation participant feedback

Results for GLAM survey 1 and GLAM survey 2 demonstrate very strong and sustained support from the cultural heritage sector on the objectives of TaNC. They also showed the highest level of importance was given for 'benefitting a diverse range of audiences'. Interesting, albeit based on a small sub-sample of individuals involved in projects, survey findings showed that this objective was seen as having the most room for TaNC to improve on.

Furthermore, feedback and suggestions were given on TaNC's governance and accountability; funding and resourcing of projects; bringing projects together and policy recommendations made at the end of 2024.

⁶ [Projects | Towards a National Collection](#)

⁷ Alma Economics (2024) Towards a National Collection: Total Economic Value of a unified digital collection. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12755041>

Future investment

GLAM sector surveys revealed, the order of priority for future investment from highest to lowest:

1. Training and support for digital skills.
2. Increased digitisation.
3. A source of technical development and expertise.
4. Guidance on copyright, licensing and open access.

In the sector surveys, the GLAM sector took pains to point out differences between cataloguing and digitisation. They highlighted digital-born collections in addition to digitisation of analogue collections. GLAM sector workers expressed concern that collections were not publicly accessible, including in the digital sphere, and welcomed resource to improve cataloguing and digitisation backlogs.

Evaluation participants were supportive of training and support for digital skills, but aware of challenges within the GLAM sector, and indeed the HEI sector.

In all cases evaluation participants were actively thinking about how to create shared resources to help the wider GLAM sector such as skills hubs, digital repositories and more.

Reflections from evaluation participants are included on:

- Value from future investment
- Inclusivity of future investment
- Risks of future investment
- Sustainability of future investment

The end reports of Discovery Projects provide a more comprehensive account of technical and non-technical recommendations spanning from each.

As this final quote from a Discovery Project participant illustrates, the legacy of TaNC needs taken forward by individuals, HEIs and IROs, GLAM organisations and partners, policy makers and funders:

'Our project comes to an end, people are now buzzing with ideas about what they can do with this data and are looking for routes to take that forward and carry that work on and build on it. So, so I think it really has across the programme demonstrated what the potential for this kind of work is and built enthusiasm and a cohort of people with new skills and new interests and finding ways to support that in future.'

1. Introduction

As with any programme evaluation, it is crucial to understand what has worked well, areas for development and learning which can go towards this programme and future efforts. TaNC's evaluation was commissioned towards 'building a compelling case for funding beyond the current five-year programme to support UK digital collections research infrastructure'.

As a minimum, the evaluation was commissioned to assess TaNC's impact on cultural institutions':

- Policy and strategy.
- Digital capacity and capability.
- Ambitions for growth and development of their digital collections.

In addition, the evaluation was also commissioned to assess TaNC's effectiveness at:

- Promoting interdisciplinary working.
- Developing partnerships between the academic and cultural heritage sectors.
- Building a community with a shared vision.

Figure 1.1: Evaluation Phases

Diffley Partnership developed an evaluation approach in phases (see figure 1.1), including a Theory of Change (ToC) model (see section 3.2).

The research towards the Phase 1 interim evaluation report was undertaken between award of contract on 6 March 2023 to 27 July 2023.⁸ This was the interim point, where it was expedient to analyse and distil the interim findings to inform policy recommendations, as well as any recommendations for adjustments within the remainder of the programme. Phase 2 of the evaluation commenced 14 August 2024 and concluded 28 February 2025. Much of the primary engagement of Phase 2 took place before the final programme conference on 20 and 21 November 2024, which saw the launch of two core programme outputs: 1) Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections – A Call to Action⁹ and 2) Towards Digital Collections: Resources for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums¹⁰. Additionally, Phase 2 concluded before the publication of final reports for Discovery Projects in January and February 2025.

This final evaluation report opens with a brief chapter on key context on TaNC, relevant for this evaluation. The next chapter provides details of the evaluation approach, methodology, fieldwork and analysis.

Chapters four, five and six contain findings about the impact of TaNC. These are organised under impacts for: cultural heritage organisations; collections and their audiences; digital collections research ecosystem.

Chapter seven contains key participant feedback on TaNC, including perceptions of TaNC's progress towards its original objectives, and feedback on the programme.

In conclusion, chapter eight focuses on future priorities. This brings together the desires expressed in published reports and the primary research conducted towards the evaluation. This chapter is intended to be of value to those involved in maximising the legacy of TaNC, learning lessons and building on successes.

⁸ Diffley Partnership (2023). Impact Evaluation Interim Report (Towards a National Collection). Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8269842>

⁹ Bailey, Rebecca, Pereda, Javier, Michaels, Chris, & Callahan, Tom. (2024). Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections. A call to action. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838916>

¹⁰ Ex Nihilo in partnership with University of Oxford (2024) Towards Digital Collections; Resources for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums: https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/9719434/pages/welcome-to-towards-digital-collections?module_item_id=114107389

2. Context of TaNC

2.1 Funding

The UK Research and Innovation's (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF) has funded 34 programmes involving multi- and interdisciplinary research organised under eight themes:¹¹

1. Environment.
2. Biology and biomedicine.
3. Artificial intelligence.
4. Productivity.
5. Infrastructure.
6. Health, wellbeing and human rights.
7. Digital.
8. Productivity and technical.

TaNC was awarded £18.9 million within the digital theme of SPF. It is delivered by the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) and supported by the UK government's Department for Culture Media and Sport (DCMS) and AHRC's independent research organisations.¹²

TaNC was awarded to run from 2020 to 2025 with a list of partners involved, including AHRC.¹³ The scope and activities were described as follows:¹⁴

'By seizing the opportunity presented by new digital technology, it will allow researchers to:

- Formulate radically new research questions
- Increase visitor numbers
- Dramatically expand and diversify virtual access to our heritage, and
- Bring clear economic, social and health benefits to communities across the UK.

The innovation driven by the programme will maintain the UK's world leadership in digital humanities and set global standards in the field.'

2.2 Aims and objectives of TaNC

The objectives of TaNC were to:

- Begin to dissolve barriers between different collections.
- Open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research.

¹¹ [Strategic Priorities Fund – UKRI](#)

¹² [Strategic Priorities Fund – UKRI](#)

¹³ [Towards a national collection – opening UK heritage to the world – UKRI](#)

¹⁴ [Towards a national collection – opening UK heritage to the world – UKRI](#)

- Extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location.
- Benefit a diverse range of audiences.
- Be active and of benefit across the UK.
- Provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward.¹⁵

TaNC was set out to have a transformative impact on:

- Digital search and cataloguing tools for collections, and related technologies and methodologies.
- Research capability: through enhanced researcher access and new cross-collection search tools, researchers will be able to exploit the potential of the nation’s research assets in innovative ways, addressing radically new research questions and thereby maintaining UK global leadership in inter-disciplinary research.
- Public access and public engagement with heritage: the programme will generate research-driven public-facing outputs, including major new exhibitions and immersive installations; extend public access beyond collections’ physical location, nationally and internationally; and facilitate wider and better-informed public engagement.

In this report, we usually use the terms ‘cultural heritage sector’ and ‘cultural heritage organisations’ to refer to the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) sector and institutions, in reference to such institutions’ work to ‘collect and maintain cultural heritage materials in the public interest.’¹⁶

2.3 Projects

TaNC’s competitive funding calls for Foundation Projects and Discovery Projects were planned from the outset. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, another call was added for COVID-19 Urgency Projects (hereafter named as COVID-19 Projects).

Eight small-scale Foundation Projects began in February 2020 and all were completed by July 2022. The projects aimed to lay the foundations for a virtual national collection by identifying and addressing the current or future challenges facing the formation of such a collection. Each project was a collaboration between at least one Independent Research Organisation (IRO) and one Higher Education Institution, and includes relevant non-IRO organisations.

Three COVID-19 Projects were awarded, with the first starting in January 2021, and all were completed by March 2022. Projects were selected to provide a critical and time-sensitive evaluation of the digital practice undertaken by museums during the COVID-19 pandemic and provide scalable lessons to inform future museum practice as well as the overall TaNC programme.

Five major Discovery Projects began in October 2021 and were all completed by January 2025. These extended across the UK, involving 15 universities, 63 heritage collections and institutions of different scales, with over 120 individual researchers and collaborators. These aimed to research and develop emerging

¹⁵ [Towards a National Collection - Research and scholarship \(nationalarchives.gov.uk\)](https://nationalarchives.gov.uk)

¹⁶ [GLAM \(cultural heritage\) - Wikipedia](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GLAM_(cultural_heritage))

technologies, including machine learning and citizen-led archiving, in order to connect the UK's cultural artefacts and historical archives in new and transformative ways.

Projects were carried out by a combination of organisations including:

- UK Higher Education Institutions (HEIs),
- Independent Research Organisations (IROs),¹⁷
- cultural organisations.

2.4 Programme-level initiatives

The TaNC programme had several regular communications avenues:

- Website: [Towards a National Collection](#).
- Twitter/ X: [Towards a National Collection](#).
- Bluesky: [Towards a National Collection](#).
- Mailing list.

A blog feature was created for the website but has not been populated to date.¹⁸ In practice, the News section was kept up to date.¹⁹

The Programme Directorate ensured:

- All TaNC outputs are published on [Zenodo](#), an open dissemination research data repository which preserves and makes available research and educational and informational content.
- Recordings of events were hosted on [YouTube](#).

Furthermore, the Programme Directorate have arranged:

- International webinars on digital public engagement strategies,²⁰ copyright and open access for digital collections,²¹ on international initiatives Digital NZ, Japan Search, CulturalItalia and Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek,²² African and Indigenous Futures,²³ Linking Digital Collections Globally.²⁴
- Webinars on commissioned research including the Value of Digital UK Collections.²⁵
- Project webinars.
- Conference: *Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections*, London, 26 April 2023.
- Conference: *Driving Innovation through Digital Collections*, Manchester, 20 and 21 November 2024.

¹⁷ For a full list of IROs see: [Eligible independent research organisations and catapult centres – UKRI](#)

¹⁸ [Blog | Towards a National Collection](#)

¹⁹ [PROJECT NEWS | Towards a National Collection](#)

²⁰ [TaNC Webinar: Digital Public Engagement Strategies - YouTube](#)

²¹ [TaNC Webinar: Copyright and Open Access for Digital Collections: a Roundtable Discussion - YouTube](#)

²² [TaNC Webinar: CulturalItalia & Deutsche Digitale Bibliothek Webinar - YouTube](#)

²³ [African & Indigenous Futures: Harnessing AI for Global South Languages | Towards a National Collection](#)

²⁴ [Linking Digital Collections Globally | Towards a National Collection](#)

²⁵ [The Value of Digital UK Collections | Towards a National Collection](#)

2.5 External Influences

A number of external influences were highlighted to be acknowledged and explored within the evaluation. These included:

- Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, including for the wider economy as well as the financial situation and staffing resource of HEIs, IROs and the wider cultural heritage sector. Original timings and sequencing of Foundation and Discovery Projects were altered as a result.
- EU Exit, including repercussions for funding availability for UK HEIs and changes to freedom of movement and goods affecting IROs and other cultural heritage organisations.
- Given TaNC relates to digital records, it is subject to more specific influences such as copyright and licencing, which present barriers to sharing data.

Lastly, as a programme, TaNC may be influenced by the expectations of its funder UKRI, AHRC and TaNC's Steering Committee. UKRI are looking to assess the knowledge, economic and societal impacts of SPF and its programmes, including:²⁶

- New and improved public policy (regulations, frameworks, programmes, taxes, subsidies).
- New and improved public services (infrastructure, health, welfare, education).
- New and improved products and services.

2.6 Timeline

Figure 2.1 shows the timeline for the overall programme, the project types and the programme evaluation commission.

Figure 2.1: Timeline

²⁶ [Strategic Priorities Fund: baseline and interim process evaluation – UKRI](#)

3. Methodology

3.1 Evaluation approach

Based on the evaluation brief and successful proposal, an evaluation approach and framework were designed by Diffley Partnership. Their engagement as evaluators commenced in March 2023.

Diffley Partnership examined the public information on the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) Strategic Priorities Fund (SPF), through which TaNC was funded (see section 2.1 for more information).²⁷ The Baseline and Interim Process Evaluation Technical Report (V3), published September 2021, included recommendations for Programme-level evaluation.²⁸

3.2 Theory of change model

A theory of change (ToC) is a description of why a particular way of working will be effective, showing how change happens in the short, medium and long term to achieve the intended impact. In some cases, ToC models are developed at the start of a programme to aid with strategic planning in other cases, they are developed for existing programmes to aid with evaluation.

The ToC model developed to aid the evaluation of TaNC is represented in a visual diagram (see Appendix A). This was discussed between the TaNC Programme Directorate and Diffley Partnership.

As this ToC model was for an existing programme, it plotted existing features of TaNC.

The assumptions behind the ToC model include:

- Overall programme rationale was established at the start and funded through SPF accordingly (see section 2.1).
- There are links between the success of TaNC's projects and the success of the overall TaNC programme.
- TaNC projects were hugely diverse and did not necessarily speak to all of TaNC's programme objectives.

²⁷ [Strategic Priorities Fund – UKRI](#)

²⁸ [3484 SPF Evaluation DFR Technical Report V3 220623 \(ukri.org\)](#)

3.3 Evaluation stages

The Interim Evaluation Report was published by the TaNC Programme Directorate in August 2023.²⁹ That report includes findings based on primary and secondary sources available at the time. Covid Projects and Foundation Projects were completed, but Discovery Projects were still ongoing.

As was always intended, there was then a pause in engagement, during which the evaluators and the Programme Directorate held a couple of keep in touch meetings, mainly for the evaluators to understand changes in timelines of TaNC delivery. Evaluation engagement then recommenced in August 2024, culminating in this final evaluation report.

3.4 Secondary analysis

The research team were very conscious of not duplicating efforts and minimising the burden of taking part in this evaluation for research participants. As such, desk research was incorporated as an important part of the evaluation. Table 3.1 shows the desk sources consulted for the interim evaluation and final evaluation stages. See Appendix B for full references and links to all published reports.

Table 3.1: Desk materials

Type	For Interim Evaluation	For Final Evaluation
Commissioned reports	7	4
TaNC Programme authored reports	n/a	3
Foundation Projects- Interim Reports	8	n/a
Foundation Projects Final Reports	8	n/a
COVID-19 Projects Final Reports	3	n/a
Discovery Projects First Reports	5	n/a
Discovery Projects Second Reports	5	n/a
Discovery Projects Final Reports	n/a	5
Discovery Projects additional outputs	n/a	1

²⁹ [Impact Evaluation Interim Report \(Towards a National Collection\)](#)

3.5 Engagement sessions

Engagement sessions were designed to hear from those involved in TaNC projects (see table 3.1).

Participants were invited through the TaNC Programme Directorate, making clear that the research was being conducted by independent researchers. Diffley Partnership followed up with each project to arrange a date and time. Through email and the meeting invite, they ensured information was provided to potential participants; a Privacy Notice was shared in advance and informed consent was ensured. It was made clear that TaNC Programme Directorate were not attending any sessions, nor receiving any recordings.

Discussion Guides were prepared in advance (see Appendix C) and discussion topics followed the order of:

- Background and introduction.
- TaNC objectives.
- Project reflections relevant for the programme evaluation.
- Collaboration.
- Future Focus.

In this report, themes from the evaluation sessions are included. Where the findings are similar or different those from the interim evaluation stage, this is explained in the report. For the fuller interim evaluation findings, please refer to the Interim Evaluation report.³⁰

Quotes from the engagement sessions are not attributed to individuals, instead they are labelled with [COVID-19 participant] or [Foundation participant] or [Discovery participant].

Table 3.1: Engagement session participants

	For Interim Evaluation	For Final Evaluation	Total
Focus Group sessions	5	6	11
Focus Group dates	24 May 2023 25 May 2023 26 May 2023 6 June 2023 8 June 2023	11 September 2024 5 November 2024 14 November 2024 27 November 2024 18 December 2024 13 January 2025	
Participants by project type			
COVID-19 Projects	5	n/a	45
Foundation Projects	11	n/a	
Discovery Projects	n/a	29	

³⁰ [Impact Evaluation Interim Report \(Towards a National Collection\)](#)

Towards the final evaluation, evaluators organised two additional evaluation sessions at the request of Discovery Project members who could not make the time and date which had been scheduled with each project. These were mixed sessions for members of different projects, the first of which was conducted, and participants took part. The second did not proceed as there was no uptake to take part. Therefore, there was an evaluation session for each of the five projects, and one mixed session, making six sessions in total.

3.6 Sector survey

An online survey was designed for the UK's wider Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums (GLAM) sector, including employees, students and volunteers. Academics were not engaged in this research, as they were the subject of separate consultations.

A snowball promotion technique was taken to reach the cultural heritage sector. This involved utilisation of TaNC methods of communications (see section 2.4 for links to these) and emails requesting that organisations across the cultural heritage sector promote the opportunity to take part in the survey through their communications avenues.

It was made clear that this research was being conducted by Diffley Partnership. A bespoke privacy notice was created for the survey.

The survey (see Appendix F) began by introducing the purpose of the survey, towards the TaNC evaluation, and then asked questions within the following sections in order:

- About your role and organisation.
- Familiarity with TaNC.
- Experience of TaNC.
- UK cultural heritage sector and digital collections developments.

This survey was first issued 22 June to 19 July 2023 and generated 193 responses.

This survey was slightly updated and then repeated approximately a year and a half later, from 1 November 2024 to 3 January 2025. For this second wave, the survey achieved 134 responses.

Where survey results are included in this report, they are referred to as GLAM survey 1 and GLAM survey 2.

4. Findings- Impacts for Cultural Heritage Organisations

4.1 Introduction

This findings chapter includes results on TaNC’s organisational-level impacts for cultural heritage organisations.

Survey respondents with involvement in TaNC (21) were asked on an agreement scale about TaNC’s impacts on their organisation in the GLAM sector survey 1 and 2. Results are shown in figure 4.1 for those who rated each statement within this question in GLAM sector survey 2.

Figure 4.1: Do you agree or disagree that TaNC has resulted in the following?

Table 4.1: Results on statements on TaNC’s impacts for GLAM surveys 1 and 2

GLAM Survey	Survey 1- Summer 2023	Survey 2- Winter 2024/2025
Most positive about these results from TaNC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped us develop collaborations with other organisations – 19 in agreement; 3 in disagreement. Helped us improve working across different disciplines – 15 in agreement; 7 in disagreement. Helped us to be innovative – 14 in agreement; 7 in disagreement. Helped us develop partnerships with the higher education sector – 13 in agreement; 9 in disagreement. Helped us engage with public audiences – 13 in agreement; 8 in disagreement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped us develop collaborations with other organisations – 13 in agreement; 2 in disagreement. Helped us improve working across different disciplines – 10 in agreement; 5 in disagreement. Helped us to be innovative – 10 in agreement; 4 in disagreement. Helped us develop partnerships with the higher education sector – 11 in agreement; 4 in disagreement. Helped us engage with public audiences – 8 in agreement; 5 in disagreement.
Mixed views on the following results from TaNC:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped us improve digital search of collections records – 11 in agreement; 10 in disagreement. Helped skills development in our organisation – 10 in agreement; 11 in disagreement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped skills development in our organisation – 8 in agreement; 6 in disagreement.
Most negative towards TaNC in these areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy – 9 in agreement; 13 in disagreement. Helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability – 7 in agreement; 15 in disagreement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy – 5 in agreement; 8 in disagreement. Helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability – 5 in agreement; 8 in disagreement. Helped us improve digital search of collections records – 6 in agreement; 8 in disagreement.

Results for GLAM survey 1 and GLAM survey 2 are categorised in table 4.1. Interpretations of results should be mindful that impacts can take time to materialise. Furthermore, for GLAM survey 1, only 25 people involved in TaNC and working for cultural heritage organisations responded to this question, a sub-set of the wider sample of 193; for GLAM survey 2, 15 people involved in TaNC and working for cultural heritage organisations responded to this question, a sub-set of the wider sample of 134.

The sections below bring in further evidence from the engagement sessions and desk research towards those areas with the most negative results from GLAM survey 2- improving digital policy and strategy, improving digital capacity and capability and improving digital search.

4.2 Policy and strategy

Surveys with the GLAM sector indicated that impact on policy and strategy may be an area for improvement. In GLAM survey 2, for the statement, 'helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy', five were in agreement, while eight were in disagreement.

At the interim evaluation stage, participants in the engagement sessions from within and without the cultural heritage sector gave some examples of how their TaNC project(s) informed their organisations' policy and strategy. Others felt that they had already been working in this space and appreciated the chance to further this work, even if it did not substantially alter their strategy. All were keen for insights from TaNC at a programme-level to inform policy and strategy at a national-level.

Turning back to the question of whether TaNC has led to improvements in policy and strategy of organisations, Discovery Projects have made more strides in this respect. This is simply because they are longer and larger projects than Foundation and Covid Projects. Also, people working for IROs explained how TaNC made a difference:

'Just the opportunity to think about something quite visionary and experimental was, we wouldn't, you know, get that opportunity every day. So it has sort of provoked us into conversations around policies to do with AI and our collections data, etcetera.'

In their final report, the Sloane Lab explained how the project impacted the digital policies and practices of the GLAM partners, pointing to a continued legacy for those IRO institutions:³¹

'Sloane Lab has had clear implications for the future work of the British Museum, Natural History Museum and other partners as they develop their own long-term strategies for their digital collections. For the BM and NHM, the project has enabled new work on one of the founding collections of the BM (and de facto founding collection of the NHM) to be continued, and on a scale not otherwise possible without the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) programme. The generation of new data and integration of data permits new ways of querying the collection and the analysis of the data provides new insights. These insights include how digital methods may help us to better understand the legacies of transatlantic enslavement, empire, and colonialism, and how they are as present in digital cultural heritage data as in the physical museum itself... Sloane Lab also challenges the BM to work out how best to support and structure the people and the digital infrastructure needed to support the future of digital collections envisaged by TaNC. As such, the Sloane Lab collections-based research has resulted in new paradigms for heritage organisations who work with challenging collections, opening new conversations and partnerships that explore questions about who gets to rethink, to contribute to and shape collections and exhibitions, to reach

³¹ Nyhan, Julianne, Vlachidis, Andreas, Flinn, Andrew, Pearlman, Nina, Carine, Mark, & Hill, Jeremy. (2025). Final Report - Sloane Lab: Looking Back to Build Future Shared Collections, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14771754>

across institutional boundaries, subject-specialities and even countries to better engage varied audiences and partnerships.'

Despite finding evidence of TaNC being a positive influence on policy and strategy in larger, national organisations involved, evaluation participants raised the question of whether a difference was made to smaller GLAM organisations involved or to the wider GLAM sector. Transferability of learning beyond IROs was desired by Discovery Project participants.

As was the case at interim evaluation stage, there was an expectation that TaNC would advance policy and strategy discussions at a UK level (see section 7.6 for more feedback on TaNC's policy recommendations). Some evaluation participants were keen to understand what meetings and discussions were taking place between the TaNC Programme Directorate and UKRI, or with cultural sector portfolios within England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales. Others had the impression that conversations would be taking place 'behind closed doors' and TaNC's 'leadership' would be trying to make the case for future funding and initiatives (see section 6.5 for findings on exemplars to supporting funding).

4.3 Digital capacity and capability

As already mentioned, GLAM survey 2 results indicated that impact on digital capacity and capability is an area for improvement. For the statement, 'helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability', five respondents were in agreement and eight were in disagreement. Furthermore, for 'helped skills development in our organisation', eight respondents were in agreement; but six were in disagreement. The engagement sessions expanded on these findings for capacity, capability and skills.

At the interim evaluation stage, one engagement session participant explained their project focused on digital capability amongst small organisations. Other participants explained that being part of the project team had benefitted them directly. However, it was also noted that the wider impact of this skills development would depend on any future use of projects' findings:

'For those involved in the projects, we have all developed skills, but in terms of broader, sector-wide skills, that depends on what happens after TaNC.' [COVID-19 participant]

One participant from the GLAM sector explained:

'Our data sets are relatively small compared to things, the majority of things in computer science or large language models. And that creates a very different source set which needs supporting in a different way. So I think, to be boring, I think that investment in people, particularly in this sector is really important if you want to reap those benefits of advanced computational capability. Because there's no doubt we can harvest more stuff and do more things and create more links. But it's the veracity and value of those links which I think at the moment, you'd have some concerns over.'
[Discovery participant]

Another explained how skills, capacity and capability within the GLAM sector depends on creation and sustained budgets for staffing:

'Institutions actually don't know how to change themselves. And so, if there is going to be a pot of money that, actually one of the most important parts of money is actually going to need to fund long-term staffing in some of our organisations to make the change happen.' [Discovery participant]

In November 2024, TaNC's Programme Directorate published training materials.³² These were aimed at small and medium-sized organisations. Training events and workshops were planned for January to March 2025 across the UK. At the evaluation stage, it is not possible to tell the extent to which these are being utilised. However, their availability does indicate that making knowledge from TaNC useful to the broader GLAM sector and its workforce was considered.

Looking back at skills within the Discovery Projects, evaluation session participants described a scramble to secure a limited number of skilled people to form projects. This skills shortage also applied to researchers within higher education institutions:

'When we had to employ three people working on the technical area of the projects on different tasks, but within the, you know, the broader technical umbrella, we found it extremely difficult to recruit because at the time that we were recruiting, also the other five projects recruiting similar skills. And it seemed like that it was a shortage of this kind of skills. People with, you know, information computing, data science, intersecting with humanities, you know, and being able to operate at the level that we want them to operate. Yeah, having good technical skills, but also good appreciation of the domain and the challenges there...I feel like TaNC has done this, you know, we've seen the fruits now because one of our PDRAs now has been employed as an expert in Canada and they can, you know, these people, they would be seen as world leading figures in what we do.' [Discovery participant]

'In the time scale of this project, you did not necessarily have enough time, for example, in the programming, programming of Immersive systems, VR skills. You didn't have some time to pick somebody up who didn't have those skills and then bringing them up to speed that, even though that's literally taught in the, in this department...So we're in a position where we needed people with those skills in hand ready to go from the get go. And that proved quite tricky, I have to say, to be honest with you, because of the time frame. We were competing in the marketplace where actually, I mean this goes up and down over time, but a couple of years ago, they were, they were quite marketable skills and people were getting offered longer term contracts with more money outside academia.' [Discovery participant]

At final evaluation stage, those taking part in evaluation sessions explained how in-roads had been made during the Discovery Projects. This was helped by the Discovery projects' length and duration, with opportunities for skills development, for example:

³² Ex Nihilo in partnership with University of Oxford (2024) Towards Digital Collections; Resources for Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums: https://canvas.instructure.com/courses/9719434/pages/welcome-to-towards-digital-collections?module_item_id=114107389

'I think, in the first year without a data scientist on the team...I think we were extremely worried and I think we sort of identified that, really, there wasn't a career path for heritage data science. There was no such thing. And actually, I think that what these three-year projects have done is to actually show what, what that career path might look like.' [Discovery participant]

The final report of Congruence Engine explained initial concerns securing data science specialists were overcome by the project:³³

'We shared with other Discovery Projects the core initial difficulty of recruiting data scientists. Here we have some grounds for optimism that the TaNC programme itself may have begun to make inroads in what seemed in 2022 to be an insuperable difficulty: there existed no model career path for heritage data science. At that point this felt like a defining issue of humanities-heritage-computational interdisciplinary work. We also feared at the start that there were major differences in the work culture expectations of these three sectors: that good humanities research is comfortable with open-endedness; heritage workers mainly do practical problem-solving, and computing professionals manage risk within a contract-framed model of delivery. In the end, and especially through the project's 'second era' of intensive digital investigations, we found that collaborative working across disciplines, and researchers' appetite for working in a hybrid fashion created models of practice, and individuals, who will be able to take this work forward.'

4.4 Improving digital search

In GLAM survey 1, amongst the sub-sample of those involved in TaNC, most were in agreement that TaNC 'helped us improve digital search of collections records'. Through the engagement sessions towards the interim evaluation of TaNC, it became apparent that development of digital collections had been enabled through the Foundation and COVID-19 Projects, to an extent. Moreover, there were ambitions for further growth and development, and participants were looking forward to the outcomes of Discovery Projects.

However, by GLAM survey 2, most involved in TaNC disagreed that TaNC 'helped us improve digital search of collections records', with six in agreement and eight in disagreement. Albeit a small sample size, this finding needs to be investigated further to understand why any GLAMs involved in TaNC projects did not feel this was improved. This evaluation revealed three possible explanations.

Firstly, a useful source of context was commissioned by TaNC itself. Collections Trust carried out a Digital Collections Audit, September 2021 to January 2022.³⁴ The aim of the audit was to 'understand the number, scale and attributes of digitally accessible collections across the UK cultural heritage sector that might form part of a future national digital collection infrastructure.' Indeed, this audit gave the most comprehensive

³³ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

³⁴ Gosling, Kevin, McKenna, Gordon, & Cooper, Adrian. (2022). Digital Collections Audit. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379581>

picture to date of digital collections held by UK institutions and where these are available. Its findings show disparity between a group of GLAM organisations and the rest of the sector:³⁵

- 230 institutions participating in the audit held nearly 146 million item-level records.
- The British Library (BL), The National Archives (TNA), BBC Archives and Natural History Museum (NHM) together account for just over half of the item-level records.
- A quarter of these item level records, 37m in all, have associated images or other digital media.
- Group level records are held by 188 of the 230 institutions (82%).
- Far fewer group records were reported than item level ones: just under 8m.
- BL, NHM, the National Library of Wales (NLW), Bradford Museums and Galleries, and another IRO between them hold 54% of all group records reported.
- Taking the 146m item level records and 8m group level records together gives a total of around 154m collection records within internal systems.
- Over 82% of the 230 respondents (190) said they publish at least some records on their own website.
- 40 of the 230 institutions (17%) only publish records online via third party aggregators and other platforms (that is, not on their own website).

Secondly, engagement sessions with Discovery projects revealed that even working with these organisations who hold a sizable proportion of cultural sector records took a lot of groundwork and time to set up data before the project could start in earnest:

'Data aggregation at the level of, of metadata for the types of records we were dealing with was fairly, well, I wouldn't say straightforward. There's a lot of work involved in it, actually a lot of work in just aligning that metadata, not trivialising that at all. But in terms of moving towards a kind of meaningful thematic links within those connections using an infrastructure like Linked open data, RDF or whatever we're, I think we're still, we've got a long way to go there. And there's a strong recognition in the project that, although we deployed AI for various types of data enhancement, is that actually, there's probably not super easy ways of creating the links between data and collections and non-digitised and digitised content...that can't really be done meaningfully algorithmically or programmatically. There's still, it requires, a human effort.' [Discovery participant]

This challenge had already been raised at the time of the interim evaluation. Foundation Projects explained that it would have been ideal for Foundation Projects to end, take stock and then have time to reconfigure and build on that work when bidding for Discovery Projects – effectively sequencing a smaller-scale project into a large-scale project.

³⁵ Gosling, Kevin, McKenna, Gordon, & Cooper, Adrian. (2022). Digital Collections Audit. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379581>

However, as explained in the commissioned Consolidation Report for Foundation Projects:³⁶

'In the initial design of Towards a National Collection, the Foundation Projects also had a major role in feeding into the subsequent Discovery Projects. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, this initial timeline changed, impacting the through-line between each phase of the programme.'

The re-configuring of time frames due to the Covid-19 pandemic likely affected the potential for Foundation Projects to set the groundwork and Discovery Projects to build on their foundations.

Thirdly, throughout the evaluation, many engagement participants and respondents to the GLAM sector surveys mentioned the ongoing work to digitise cultural heritage collections. Interestingly, this was largely framed as an endeavour which could be completed, but was subject to funding and resource. Frustrations were expressed by members of the sector, particularly in regards to a feeling that small organisations were facing more challenges than national organisations and IROs.

One evaluation participant who worked for an IRO was largely positive about the project, but explained how the final output of their Discovery Project did not fully meet what they hoped for:

'It doesn't work in the way that, as a heritage organisation, we would want it to work and want to be able to actually use it....we don't necessarily feel that we've achieved exactly what we wanted to achieve with the project. But the project, and if we had more time, we could go back and, and work on it and, and get things to work a little bit better for what, how we want to actually use it for research. But the time and the money ran out. So, we are where we are.' [Discovery participant]

Views on digital developments pertaining to dissolving barriers between collections are discussed further in section 5.2.

4.5 Conclusion

GLAM survey 2 respondents involved in TaNC projects were most positive that TaNC:

- Helped us develop collaborations with other organisations.
- Helped us improve working across different disciplines.
- Helped us to be innovative.
- Helped us engage with public audiences.
- Helped us develop partnerships with the higher education sector.

Views were more mixed that TaNC:

- Helped skills development in our organisation.

And were more negative in their view that TaNC:

- Helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy.

³⁶ Paltrinieri, Carlotta. (2023). p. 5.

- Helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability.
- Helped us improve digital search of collections records.

There was an expectation that TaNC's Programme Directorate would be advancing discussions at higher policy levels, which may lead to benefits for the GLAM sector.

There was evidence, for organisations heavily involved in TaNC, that digital policy and strategy was improved. Certainly, TaNC Discovery Projects provided opportunities for IROs to explore, discuss and update some of their policies and procedures. Also, for those funded through TaNC projects, digital capacity and capability were improved for the project durations.

However, there is currently no evidence that TaNC directly improved the digital policies and strategies or the digital capacity and capability of the other GLAM partner organisations in Discovery Projects. There was also concern expressed throughout the evaluation that TaNC may not have had significant impact on smaller, non-national GLAM organisations (see section 7.4 for more impressions of funding of projects).

Having said that, many evaluation materials explained the challenges facing the GLAM sector regarding long-standing limitations with digital policies, workforce skills and funding levels. Although hopeful that TaNC will lead to transformational change benefitting the whole sector, this is seen as more achievable following the end of Discovery Projects as part of the legacy in 2025 and onwards.

Chapter five includes findings towards impacts for collections and their audiences. Therefore, chapter five expands on some of the areas the sector survey respondents were more positive about, including working across disciplines and engaging with public audiences.

5. Findings – Impacts for Collections and their Audiences

5.1 Introduction

This findings chapter includes results on TaNC’s achievement towards four objectives all relating to collections and their audiences:

- Begin to dissolve barriers between different collections.
- Extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location.
- Benefit a diverse range of audiences.
- Open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research.

5.2 Begin to dissolve barriers between different collections

At the interim evaluation stage, the premise of dissolving barriers was questioned. There was evidence that those involved in the TaNC COVID-19 and Foundation Projects had their reservations on dissolving barriers confirmed. Many participants emphasised the beginning aspect of this objective, discussing that they believe TaNC has begun to make headway on this, but there was no guarantee projects would develop solutions.

The audit TaNC commissioned from the Collections Trust provided evidence of some of the barriers to dissolving barriers between collections, for example:³⁷

- ‘There are huge variations in the structure and semantics for object-based descriptive metadata, especially in museums. This inhibits the ability for institutions to share and exchange information easily.
- Most of the institutions assign licences and usage rights to individual digital assets, starting with records in the related catalogue systems. These are then cascaded to digital assets (held in separate DAMS). This workflow is often manual and time consuming.
- Many staff and volunteers struggle to access and use their own data due to the limitations of legacy collections management systems.
- Few institutions are using PIDs [Persistent Identifiers], or even know what they are...there is a real risk that the millions of online records reported to this audit will, over time, turn into millions of broken links.’

³⁷ Gosling, Kevin, McKenna, Gordon, & Cooper, Adrian. (2022). Digital Collections Audit. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379581>

In GLAM survey 2, respondents were mixed on the progress TaNC made to achieve this objective. While 29% agreed that TaNC is beginning to dissolve barriers between collections, 26% disagreed and a large majority (45%) expressed that they 'don't know' how TaNC is doing on this objective (See figure 7.2a).

At a project level, there were confident assertions of progress in project reports, including:³⁸

'Overall, the Heritage Connector project demonstrated that the methods used can be used to build links at scale between and within collections.'

The Discovery Project, Unpath'd Waters, explained how bringing together maritime-related collections in a way where they could be utilised was their central aim:³⁹

'The UK has a rich maritime heritage. It is impossible to tell the story of our islands without talking about our relationship with the sea. This maritime past is becoming increasingly important. People are more aware of our exploitation of the sea and topics such as colonialism, slavery and immigration.'

Unpath'd Waters therefore sought to increase interaction with the UK's maritime heritage by making it easier to research and easier for the public to discover and share stories in new ways. Despite its importance, it is not always easy to study our maritime heritage. Records, maps and objects are scattered across hundreds of different archives, museums, libraries and galleries. A large part of our work has been to develop new ways of making information across these different collections easy to search and find.'

The final report of Congruence Engine explained their recommended concept of 'UK collections linkage':⁴⁰

'The outcome of our body of investigations (described in the annex) supports our recommendations (section 13) that centre on the creation, not of a 'national collection' (as we first termed our aspiration), but of 'UK collections linkage'. This, we propose, should be achieved by datafication of collections catalogues and via linked open data (LOD) techniques. This will entail heritage organisations expanding data held in digital form about collections items so as to enhance especially: data on the associations and purposes of objects (and other collections items), and tightening of dating. Contextual associations, including from exhibition texts, catalogues, publications and support files should also be converted into data to maximise institutional retention of narrative understanding, and thereby linkage to other collections and greatly increased research use of all kinds. Techniques including Named Entity Recognition deployed on such expanded

³⁸ Winters, Jane, Stack, John, Dutia, Kalyan, Unwin, Jamie, Lewis, Rhiannon, Palmer, Richard, & Wolff, Angela. (2022). Heritage Connector: A Towards a National Collection Foundation Project Final Report, p.1. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6022678>

³⁹ Sloane, Barney & Unpath'd Waters Consortium. (2025). Final Report - Unpath'd Waters: Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK. Towards a National Collection <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888571>

⁴⁰ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

collections data can enable linkage to associated items and histories across collections, especially by use of Wikidata (or functionally similar services).'

Furthermore, what this would consist of as a minimum:⁴¹

'A minimal infrastructure for a linked collection would include a simple data register (to record the whereabouts of data representing collections and record linkages) of the kind we have trialled (investigation 24). This could, with benefit, be accompanied by a resource index (listing ontologies, thesauruses, gazetteers, etc). Together, these could support people (heritage organisation staff, university academics and interested lay people) in the work of linking heritage collection items to each other and to other data sources.'

The Discovery Project, Transforming Collections, was underpinned from its start by critical heritage theory:

'A national collection cannot be imagined without addressing structural inequalities, engaging debates around contested heritage, and revealing contentious histories embedded in objects. In 1999, the late sociologist and cultural theorist, Stuart Hall, posed the question 'Whose heritage?'. Hall called for the 'unsettling' and 'reimagining' of heritage and nation.⁴² More than 25 years on, the need to critically question and transform notions of 'heritage' and 'nation' remains as urgent as ever.⁴³

In their engagement session, one Discovery Project explained how they had a very clear definition of national collection from the project outset, but they did not feel this corresponded to the approach of other TaNC projects or the programme overall:

'We were really clear from the start what this meant to us. National collection goes beyond IROs, and beyond GLAM sector. Those involved in project had that definition and I think I speak for all of us when I say that definition we adhered to stayed broadly the same. However, I didn't feel that the Programme Directorate had that same understanding; they thought about collections held by national institutions. Also, I don't feel that the other projects had exactly the same viewpoint as us. That isn't necessarily a problem if this had been discussed and re-visited throughout the programme. But it didn't seem to be.'

According to the Discovery Project, Our Heritage Our Stories, they delivered 'the most extensive investigation to date of UK Community-Generated Digital Content (CGDC), outlining potential mechanisms for bringing complex data from across the broader heritage landscape into a future UK national collection.' In their final

⁴¹ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

⁴² Keynote speech by Stuart Hall given on 1 November 1999 at 'Whose Heritage? The Impact of Cultural Diversity on Britain's Living Heritage', National Conference held in Manchester, UK.

⁴³ pui san lok, susan, Dalal-Clayton, Anjalie, Barton, Hannah, Rutherford, Ananda, Griffin, Christopher, Gillick, Jon, Rebernak, Jerneja, & Kaminska, Fleur. (2025). Final Report - Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14772312>

project report, they explain how CGDC is community-led and can counter the stories presented by institutions holding and interpreting records on behalf of the public:⁴⁴

‘The importance of CGDC is that when communities take control of documenting their own experiences and knowledge, they create vital threads in the fabric of our national collection. As communities capture and share their own stories, they strengthen and sustain their cultural identity. In CGDC, we find dynamic spaces where elders and young digital natives can connect, ensuring endangered traditional knowledge finds new forms of record in the digital age. Through community-led archives, groups can show how their stories evolve and remain relevant, while preserving their dialects and languages as they are actually used. By empowering communities to be the custodians of their own stories, we ensure that future generations inherit not just historical records but living, breathing cultural legacies that continue to inform and inspire. However, its nature as a distributed and generally underfunded resource means that CGDC has a significant resistance to traditional methods of linking and integration, which limits its accessibility so dramatically that such content risks being not only undervalued but overlooked. This is all the more problematic because CGDC is critical not only to completing and complementing the nation’s official historical record, but also to correcting and even contradicting it, by allowing otherwise unheard voices to speak, which in turn provides researchers and the wider public access to less familiar stories, alternative perspectives and marginalised experiences.’

Our Heritage, Our Stories identified challenges to linking CGDC data, and then addressed these through their project:⁴⁵

‘Existing solutions to CGDC integration, involving bespoke interventionist activities, proved expensive, time-consuming, and unsustainable at scale. Our approach, by contrast, consisted of a collaboration between multiple disciplines and institutions towards the development of new methods involving Artificial Intelligence-based tools to allow for the harmonisation of CGDC metadata. This harmonisation, in turn, has laid the foundation for bringing previously ‘unfindable’ and/or ‘unlinkable’ CGDC into the UK’s growing virtual national collection; a necessary and timely integration as more and more data is preserved and consumed in digital form.’

Regarding TaNC making advancements ‘towards a national collection’, the Discovery Projects explained TaNC has not created a national collection, but important steps have been taken to inform future developments:

⁴⁴ Hughes, Lorna, Alexander, Marc, Barker, Hannah, Batista-Navarro, Riza, Nenadic, Goran, Sheridan, John, Hannaford, Ewan, & Dierckx, Katrien. (2025). Final Report - Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching Community-Generated Digital Content. Towards a National Collection.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888428>

⁴⁵ Hughes, Lorna, Alexander, Marc, Barker, Hannah, Batista-Navarro, Riza, Nenadic, Goran, Sheridan, John, Hannaford, Ewan, & Dierckx, Katrien. (2025). Final Report - Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching Community-Generated Digital Content. Towards a National Collection.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888428>

‘Towards the national collection and in many respects, you know, this series of projects is towards a national collection, isn't it? We're not there yet, but these are putting in place some foundational activities really to build that national collection.’

5.3 Extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location

At the interim evaluation stage, engagement session participants described progress towards this objective. Some explained this was a key motivation for their specific projects and were reasonably confident they had met expectations. However, their comments were often qualified with the use of conditional terms such as ‘some’ within their narratives. They came back to the challenges of ensuring the public know they can access the collections and resourcing digitisation.

At the time, interim evaluation participants felt that this objective may be better met by Discovery Projects:

‘My immediate reaction is probably this objective was...the Discovery grants were much more aimed at this than the foundation grants because the Foundation grants were by and large much more about trying technologies out.’ [Foundation participant]

The Audience Agency, working in collaboration with Culture 24, was commissioned by TaNC to ‘deliver user research to understand what users want and need from a future national collection digital infrastructure.’ These findings add value to the understanding of the behaviours of members of the public engaging with digital content by GLAMs, including on their search/discovery behaviour, preferences for functionality and content and potential audiences:⁴⁶

‘Search/discovery behaviour-

- Heavily focused on knowing who/known where to look.
- Beyond this, both professionals and members of the public rely heavily on Google for search, browse and discovery.
- But despite the dominance of Google, the younger the user, the more likely they are to use an app, social media or a smart speaker instead.
- Mixed use of existing aggregators: The National Archives is highly valued, as are Art UK and BFI, with Europeana less so.
- Most users come to collections records via external search or organic links, not through a catalogue search.
- Current behaviour is oriented towards serendipity (discovery) as well as focused search, and academics saw serendipity as particularly important.

⁴⁶ Woodley, Sophia, & Towell, Patrick. (2022). User Research. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

Functionality and content-

- For public users, images, descriptive text and stories around items were as important as raw data.
- Timeline and map search are heavily valued by members of the public, as is being shown similar content.
- Paywalls and account creation are major deterrents, particularly for members of the public.
- Many users question what a 'national' collection means/includes.

Audiences-

- Members of the public who already engage with collections, and/or who are students, saw the value in the National Collection as a cultural resource in itself. Interest grows as engagement with culture, history and/or archives grows.
- Other members of the public remain to be convinced: they were only interested insofar as it could support or enrich a physical visit to a cultural organisation.
- The group most likely to be interested in a National Collection are 25-44 years old.
- Disabled users are more likely to be interested and educators see increasing access for disabled students as an important part of the value proposition.'

In GLAM survey 2, for those respondents involved in TaNC, eight agreed that TaNC helped them to engage with public audiences and five disagreed.

Evaluation participants felt the starting point for extending access should be establishing what potential users would find most valuable. One explained their co-design approach found what was most important, but then fulfilling that desire is difficult:

'We started the co-design process by basically asking them really open questions about their interest in heritage and what they might be interested in researching and what kind of stories they might want to tell. We discovered very early on that the data as structured does not really support those types of, of queries and investigations. A theme that came out a lot in the conference for those of us who were there, which also came out in our work package very strongly, was that people are particularly interested in personal connections. And actually, if you look at the records, you know, whether it being hypocritical about this, if you look at the records, they're kind of bereft of people, you know. They're kind of, they're records about physical things and places. If you're interested in people and finding people's stories, how do you then, you've got to do the research. And that takes quite a lot of specialty to like, to know how to use the records and bring them out.' [Discovery participant]

In the final report for Congruence Engine, they explain the access patterns which are already enacted for different user groups of collections, and the difference their TaNC project sought to make to these linkages at a UK-level.⁴⁷

‘The capacity to make strong connections between historical objects and sources lies at the heart of this project as it does in the everyday museum and historical practices that it is designed to support. Curators creating displays combine artefacts, images, audio-visual materials and histories often drawn from several heritage organisations. Family and local historians connect records from a diversity of sources that illuminate ancestors and localities so as to establish their genealogy or to understand the past of where they live. Academic historians patiently and critically connect a diverse range of archive sources with existing literature to tell new stories about the past. All rely on connecting different fragments of the past as they sew the quilts of narrative that constitute our local, national and international histories. The difference with this Towards a National Collection project is that it seeks to make such linkages at the national scale of all collections, enabling access together to significant numbers of relevant items from across many GLAM organisations holding heritage in many media. In place of the two-dimensional ranked list of search engines, with Congruence Engine, we have modelled a world in which users will be able to explore data neighbourhoods where a great diversity of information about heritage items from many sources that are deeply relevant to their investigations will be readily to hand – museum objects, archive documents, pictures, films, buildings, and the records of previous investigations and relevant activity.’

5.4 Benefit a diverse range of audiences

Many reports contain examples of exhibitions and learning programming by GLAM organisations. For example, Transforming Collections:⁴⁸

‘The collaboration with Tate Learning led to Transforming Collections’ culminating public programme, Museum x Machine x Me, which took place between 2 and 6 October 2024 across Tate Modern and Tate Britain. Museum x Machine x Me encompassed a two-day conference, practice research displays, ML workshops for the hands-on exploration of the ML tool, pop-up artwork talks and archive displays and a Late event at Tate Britain. The programme attracted almost 8,000 visitors across the week.’

⁴⁷ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

⁴⁸ pui san lok, susan, Dalal-Clayton, Anjalie, Barton, Hannah, Rutherford, Ananda, Griffin, Christopher, Gillick, Jon, Rebernak, Jerneja, & Kaminska, Fleur. (2025). Final Report - Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14772312>

Often, numbers of visitors or people engaged are reported descriptively, rather than broken down by demographic characteristics.

Results from GLAM survey 2 demonstrate the difficulty for respondents to gauge TaNC's impact on audiences, with half (50%) of respondents saying they 'don't know' how well TaNC achieved this, with the rest split between agreement (24%) and disagreement (26%) that TaNC had achieved this (See Figure 7.2a).

Through partnership working, Unpath'd Waters developed bespoke programming for visually impaired audiences:⁴⁹

'A particularly important outcome has been the opening of heritage collections to visually impaired people. A deliberate co-design approach with representatives of the visually impaired community has fundamentally shaped the design of our Unpath'd Waters VR Navigator, providing essential experience for opening access to those otherwise disadvantaged.'

As was pointed out by Discovery Projects in their reports and evaluation sessions, respondents to the GLAM survey 2 encouraged broad perspectives on who benefits from any 'national collection':

'It is vital that digital access to collections is designed with the needs of many more sectors in mind. At the moment, the focus on research or academic access is severely limiting. Commercial media uses need to be considered as well.'

'Look outwards, away from the internal needs of 'the sector.' Look to all possible conceivable digital and public uses of collections - then consider how to join collections together. What are the real needs and wants of all possible users of collections? I don't feel the project has addressed these questions.'

The experience of Congruence Engine led them to discuss technological solutions in their final report, but coupled this with the need for inclusive approaches to utilise technology in the interests of a diverse public:⁵⁰

'The work ahead requires the power of automation enabled by new Large Language Model technologies. But it intrinsically also needs the care, contribution and connections enabled by participants of all kinds: employees of heritage organisations, researchers in the universities and a diverse array of community groups and individuals with interests in history and heritage. For linkage of collections to have purpose, it must be of a kind that serves the interests and needs of people of all kinds.'

⁴⁹ Sloane, Barney & Unpath'd Waters Consortium. (2025). Final Report - Unpath'd Waters: Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK. Towards a National Collection <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888571>

⁵⁰ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

In their final report, Our Heritage, Our Stories (OHOS) explained the value of Community-Generated Digital Content (CGDC), including progress made through their project, but highlighted barriers inhibiting the GLAM sector's ability to benefit a diverse range of audiences:⁵¹

'OHOS has identified ways that stories can be captured in decentralised approaches to documentation and description, expressed in the post-custodial model of empowering communities to be the custodians in ways that connect tangible material culture to the place, identity, memories and narratives that give it meaning. However, OHOS has identified severe and structural resource constraints that affect most community heritage organisations. A lack of sustained funding for digital preservation threatens the survival of much CGDC in the medium and long term, requiring mitigating action. The project has also documented the manifold legal and ethical considerations complicating digital preservation, data integration and interlinking, particularly in terms of the strict requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) framework. Finally, OHOS has charted the various trust barriers and power differentials that exist between communities and established national heritage institutions.'

A Discovery Project participant explained how co-creation aspects of their project fundamentally changed what they initially set out to do:

'Projects are inevitably produced at the conceptual level, by those who are invested, interested on a specific subject. And then how that translate in terms of meaningfulness for communities, for people outside of that group then becomes a little bit of a discovery project in itself. So co-design then became not just in terms of the actual digital platform and the digital challenges, but it was also changed on a wider and most profound level. And I think that that that ability to rethink, re-evaluate, has been has been a challenge, but a very important one.' [Discovery participant]

Discovery Projects were keen to point out that improving the accessibility of collections records does not automatically lead to benefits for a diverse range of audience. Most fundamentally, this is because those collections and their records are subject to historical and institutional biases.

For example, as stated in the final report by Congruence Engine:⁵²

'There is work to do, not only in addressing archaic data and absences in collections, and in gaining a deeper understanding of the origins of our collections in an extractive imperial age, but also in developing approaches to equity in the forthcoming work on collections linkage that recognise the structural inequalities of our sector and in what it represents via its collections and public works.'

⁵¹ Hughes, Lorna, Alexander, Marc, Barker, Hannah, Batista-Navarro, Riza, Nenadic, Goran, Sheridan, John, Hannaford, Ewan, & Dierckx, Katrien. (2025). Final Report - Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and searching Community-Generated Digital Content. Towards a National Collection.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888428>

⁵² Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

This was echoed by various Discovery Projects in evaluation sessions:

'I think one of the, maybe, one of the challenges of the project, in some cases, that it hasn't actually really address[ed] the ontological questions within what a national collection actually is... how you're going to aggregate things to, to bring together collections, which, are you just going to reproduce the same systems of, of knowledge and power in the West or the so-called kind of universal systems.' [Discovery participant]

'I think the project was very ambitious in many ways and they had such a technical focus, and to, sometimes, to the detriment of the, of the ethical questions or the kind of more philosophical questions. I completely understand some of the ways in which the concept of a national collection is, you know, it's, it's easily digestible, like to different audiences. And you're making a case for, for heritage collections that are held within the UK. But there is an inherent, I guess, question of, of ownership within that and, or assumption of, of ownership even when they're world collections from all over the world.' [Discovery participant]

Furthermore, benefitting diverse ranges of audiences through the innovations which TaNC projects have developed is not immediate:

'This is typical of public funding where we deliver projects, but there is no follow up projects to actually map change, the impact of that project, to understand how people are transformed. Unless we observe, we sit down, we engage with people, we follow up with those participants, for example, and we see how they engage now with the resources. So to really assess transformation, you need time.' [Discovery participant]

5.5 Open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research

In GLAM survey 2, many agreed that TaNC opened up collection to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research: 34% agreed and only 17% disagreed. Around half of all respondents (49%) reported that they didn't know if this was achieved (see Figure 7.2a).

In terms of promoting interdisciplinary working, interim evaluation engagement session participants explained that this was encouraged by the very set up of the TaNC projects. Requiring different partners, requiring different specialisms and encouraging collaboration were seen as strengths of TaNC.

Even towards the final evaluation stage, the COVID-19 pandemic was seen to have affected collaboration, including:

- Financial sustainability of GLAM organisations and any commercial partners had decreased.
- As a consequence of funding and resources pressures, organisations had to re-prioritise work.
- Fewer in-person collaborative meetings than desired, albeit people were used to getting the most out of online meetings.

For example, one Discovery Project participant explained:

'I think that's a, just a sort of general point, isn't it? About the impact of the pandemic and sort of post pandemic and how that's changed work patterns. The way in which we interact with each other, what worked, what would have worked pre-pandemic didn't, doesn't necessarily work post pandemic. And that's been...an additional challenge perhaps that we've had to navigate. We probably haven't had as many in person meetings as we would have done had we been doing this project in 2019... We have actually achieved much more during those meetings than probably, you know, through online meetings.' [Discovery participant]

In their final project report, Sloane Lab explained a great deal of participatory work went towards their Sloane Lab Knowledge Base.⁵³

'Substantial human labour is necessary at crucial points of even highly automated digital workflows, from data checking and cleaning to the transcription of fonts or handwriting that still cannot be fully automated by machines. These necessary human interventions are crucial, and digital workflows such as developed by Sloane Lab, cannot function without them.'

Another contributory factor in opening up this collection to different disciplinary perspectives, was Sloane Lab's Community Fellows programme:

'The Fellowship scheme brought new voices and expertise into the Sloane Lab. The eleven fellows undertook creative, critical and practice and/or research-led projects with the Sloane Lab's Knowledge Base and data, highlighting the opportunities for analysis and interpretation unlocked by the project. The diverse Fellowship projects ranged from artistic responses to Sloane data and material related to the colonial entanglements of the collection, to data visualisation, multivocality, absence, decentralised archival systems, Black life in the Sloane collections, and women in Sloane's 'Paper Museum'. We had the aspiration, in light of the history of the collection, that at least 50% of the fellowships should be awarded to Global Majority populations. Five of the eleven fellowships were ultimately taken up by members of Global Majority populations.'

Transforming Collections was another example of a Discovery Project where cross-disciplinary working featured in its design.⁵⁴

'The project combined critical art historical and museological research with participatory and interactive machine learning (ML) design. A series of artistic research residencies engaged with emerging findings, and embedded creative activations of the research within the project's public programme. The project sought to surface suppressed histories, amplify marginalised voices, and re-evaluate artists and artworks long ignored or side-lined by dominant narratives and institutional

⁵³ Nyhan, Julianne, Vlachidis, Andreas, Flinn, Andrew, Pearlman, Nina, Carine, Mark, & Hill, Jeremy. (2025). Final Report - Sloane Lab: Looking Back to Build Future Shared Collections, Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14771754>

⁵⁴ pui san lok, susan, Dalal-Clayton, Anjalie, Barton, Hannah, Rutherford, Ananda, Griffin, Christopher, Gillick, Jon, Rebernak, Jerneja, & Kaminska, Fleur. (2025). Final Report - Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14772312>

practices. It aimed to enable search and research across collections, to surface patterns of bias and relations of power, and interrogate policies and practices of classification, categorisation, description, and display. Critically and creatively connecting, interrupting, and disrupting collections, this interdisciplinary collaboration has opened up new interpretative frames to imagine an evolving 'national collection', at once connected yet distributed.'

TaNC commissioned a user consultation to identify researchers' needs and requirements for future UK digital collections infrastructure.⁵⁵ Findings relate to:

- Digitisation, Digital Preservation, and Collaboration.
- Improved Search and Discovery.
- Connection and Interoperability.
- Long-Term and Environmental Sustainability.
- Impact and Accountability.

5.6 Conclusion

This findings chapter includes results on TaNC's achievement of four objectives all relating to collections and their audiences.

The audit TaNC commissioned from the Collections Trust provided evidence of some of the challenges to dissolving barriers between collections.⁵⁶ These challenges were echoed by evaluation participants. Furthermore, the Discovery Projects brought knowledge and understanding of constraints of existing metadata.

Discovery Projects have helped establish what is not only theoretically possible, but what is practically possible. Discovery Project final reports, and their technical recommendations set these out. For example, 'Collections Linkage' was put forward as an alternative to attempting to create 'a national collection'.

Furthermore, Discovery Projects make a meaningful contribution to considerations of what collections should, and can, be included, in 'a national collection', such as existing records held by GLAMs and community-generated content.

Evaluation participants felt the starting point for extending access should be establishing what potential users would find most valuable, rather than stick to their own presumptions. Helpfully, the Audience Agency, working in collaboration with Culture 24, was commissioned by TaNC to 'deliver user research to understand

⁵⁵ Bailey-Ross, Claire; Burgess, Emily & Papageorgiou, Panagiotis (2024). User Research: UK Gallery, Library, Archive and Museum (GLAM) Digital Collections Infrastructure. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12751226>

⁵⁶ Gosling, Kevin, McKenna, Gordon, & Cooper, Adrian. (2022). Digital Collections Audit. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6379581>

what users want and need from a future national collection digital infrastructure.’ These findings add value to the understanding of public engagement with digital content by GLAMs.⁵⁷

TaNC projects have included public programming, user research and co-design, which could be taken as evidence that TaNC benefitted audiences. Similarly, TaNC projects individually should lead to digital initiatives which are designed to benefit audiences.

All the same, the question remains as to how diverse these audience are, and with respect to which criteria, such as by demographic or geographic characteristics, these audiences are ‘diverse’. From desk materials and evaluation sessions, it was clear that people involved in TaNC are conscious, and in some cases very proactive, to ensure diversity and inclusion is at the forefront of digital developments in GLAM.

The evaluation found that different disciplinary perspectives were brought into individual TaNC projects and the overall TaNC programme. In terms of digital developments resulting through TaNC, many of these were developed to bring together collections collected by different disciplines and many were developed with end users from different disciplines or interests in mind.

Chapter six moves on to consider TaNC’s impacts for digital collections research ecosystem.

⁵⁷ Woodley, Sophia, & Towell, Patrick. (2022). User Research. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6684165>

6. Findings – Impacts for Digital Collections Research Ecosystem

6.1 Introduction

This findings chapter includes results related to the broader ecosystem for digital collections research.

As such, findings are included on achievement of two of TaNC's objectives:

- Be active and of benefit across the UK.
- Provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward.

Moreover, these are intersected by examination of TaNC developing the following:

- Partnership between academic and cultural heritage sectors.
- A community with a shared vision.

6.2 Be active and of benefit across the UK

Around a third (30%) of GLAM survey 2 respondents agreed that TaNC was active and of benefit across the UK, while a fifth (20%) disagreed. Half of all respondents (50%) reported that they didn't know if this objective had been achieved, which was a slightly lower proportion than for GLAM survey 1 (54%) (see Figure 7.2a).

There were several indicators that TaNC was active and benefit across the UK:

- The Programme Directorate was hosted by Historic Environment Scotland, based in Edinburgh.
- TaNC conferences were held in London and Manchester.
- The many organisations involved in TaNC projects, provided in Appendix D.
- The data utilised within each TaNC project, for example, Unpath'd Waters linked and enhanced national maritime heritage inventories of all four home nations – England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland, and inspired the Isle of Man to create their own inventory.
- The location of TaNC project outputs, for example, Sloane Lab's Touring Exhibition '*For the Curious and the Interested*' visited two venues – Down County Museum, Downpatrick (Northern Ireland) and Ceredigion Museum, Aberystwyth (Wales) between January and September 2024.

Despite agreeing that TaNC included projects working across the UK, some evaluation participants felt that TaNC should have taken more opportunities to be active at international levels:

I understand that obviously part of the objective of this, of this project was to draw together the four UK nations who've been working independently, you know, for good reasons, it's a good starting point and so on. But to develop an infrastructure that allows us to link together these distributed

collections without articulating with international collections, I think is a little bit, is a bit a gap.'
[Discovery participant]

All the same, programme-level initiatives (see section 2.4) had brought international partners to TaNC and vice versa.

6.3 Partnerships between academic and cultural heritage sectors

Bringing together academic and cultural heritage organisations was seen as especially important by evaluation participants, given many cultural heritage roles that involve research in day-to-day work.

There was recognition that funders in the UK make efforts to join up HEIs and other sectors, for example:

'The difference between us in Australia and US in the States, and US and actually most many parts of Europe, is, it is the way which UKRI is set up and funded research that bridges the gap between the universities and the cultural organisations. And TaNC is the product of a 20-year journey of doing that.' [Discovery participant]

Opinions were generally very positive about how the TaNC programme encouraged this combination of HEIs and GLAMs. Engagement session participants commended TaNC for bringing together academic and cultural heritage sectors, for example:

'So the academic and cultural heritage divide is one that, I don't know if the programme has really managed to bridge effectively, in terms of recruitment, in terms of project organization, in terms of a lot of different things. But on the other hand, it has made great strides too. So you know it's not something that you're going to be able to do in a year, is it, you know?' [Foundation participant]

A range of experiences was shared with the evaluators, from entirely new partnerships being forged through TaNC, to existing partnerships being enhanced. This was the case for Discovery Projects as well as for Foundation and Covid-19 Projects.

All Discovery Projects included partners across different types of organisations, for example, Unpath'd Waters described themselves as:⁵⁸

'A large project, directly involving over 80 people with contributions and support from many more. A Management Group of experts in digital humanities, marine archaeology and history, ocean science and audience engagement and evaluation led a consortium of eight universities, five Independent Research Organisations and five collaborating organisations including archaeological trusts, museums and charities. These were supported by Partners whose number grew as the project gained momentum.'

⁵⁸ Sloane, Barney & Unpath'd Waters Consortium. (2025). Final Report - Unpath'd Waters: Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK. Towards a National Collection <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888571>

Those who had many organisations involved in their projects described how this brought many benefits, but also the challenge of people getting to know one another and collaborate quickly. Even keeping in touch with all the partners could be a huge undertaking:

'I think some of this kind of comes down to a question of who's actually responsible for managing relationships within a project, because it's not a PDRA's role to be in touch with 40 different project partners and managing those relationships and those expectations. That's completely unrealistic. And that, and again, it comes down to like a bit more clarity around and, and dedication if, if good cohesive relationships between project partners are actually our core to how you're going to deliver a project and how you want people to receive the project.' [Discovery participant]

TaNc project participants acknowledged that academic institutions and cultural organisations are very different, firstly in their specialisms and expertise:

'There are so many different languages effectively spoken in English across this team with very, very disciplinary approaches and at times that cause all sorts of problems. And then we had similar challenges working with our extra partners... I still do not understand what [redacted partner] people work with do. But I have an inherent trust that they're actually good at what they do. And that's actually what it requires through this type of work- it's a level of trust in other people.' [Discovery participant]

They also pointed out how motivations and viewpoints can differ:

'This is really complicated on a way which I don't actually think any of us quite understood when we started the project, in terms of the complexity of the different elements involved, how you bring them together. And again, if there's another learning, given everyone's obsessed with interdisciplinary working and all those sorts of things, this is a, this just shows the sheer level of work commitments, ability for everybody to understand what each other speak.' [Discovery participant]

Projects had to fulfil different process requirements for various types of partners:

'I'll give you a really kind of like a quick cartoon. Picture this: Our [commercial partner] wanted a brief against which they would deliver a thing because that's how they operate; the museum wanted to know how the museum could integrate its staff and who was going to ask to for what at which time, but was quite flexible about doing things by itself; and the university needed to fill in ethics forms and do all this, that and the other.' [Discovery participant]

Projects had to bring together all these different cultures to make and then deliver agile projects:

'The biggest one for me was the, was the research culture of the different organizations. So trying to, but we didn't have a game, a fully-fledged game plan when we started the project. That's the nature of research. We knew where we wanted to try and get to, but we didn't know how we were going to get there.' [Discovery participant]

Evaluation participants raised issues of parity in the way projects were costed and budgets were costed (see chapter 7.4 for more detail).

In fact, a general observation of Discovery Projects in their engagement sessions was the volume of partners on paper did not translate well into practice. For example, one shared:

'Maintaining consistent levels of engagement with that many numbers of partners is really hard. Well, it's really hard. And actually, I think in many ways we didn't succeed. We didn't succeed with our whole cohort of project partners. Some were scarcely involved at all and some were involved a lot.' [Discovery participant]

The issue of parity was raised by organisations (see chapter 7.4 for more detail) who felt that the GLAM partners involved who were not IROs or HEIs had 'a raw deal':

'If you really want to value project partners and heritage organisations around the UK, you have to give, you have to give the support and you have to make sure there's capacity within the teams to, to give time to those relationships. And it can be in a supportive way as well, that actually helps the workflows that are needed for the project.' [Discovery participant]

Academics participating in the Discovery Projects explained how researchers coming from fields like computing were involved in co-design and co-production through TaNC projects that they would not have otherwise been exposed to. They were not just looking at how to work with the data, but how it was organised, how this originated, and what the data means to people now. This could also be a learning curve for individuals. One Principal Investigator explained some consequences for individual researchers:

'Addressing questions of colonialism within the project were really, really difficult for the technical team. Like they were completely new to these issues. And it was really, really difficult for them and really emotional and upsetting. And so having that kind of, you know, taking care of your team actually like across the kind of programme in the future is, is really, really important. I think the values and ethics work can actually underpin quite a lot of that.' [Discovery participant]

6.4 Building a community with a shared vision

At the final evaluation stage, many points were raised about how Discovery Projects interacted together (see section 7.5 for more on feedback on bringing projects together). Projects, such as Congruence Engine, gave examples of connections, and also lost opportunities:⁵⁹

'Apart from... two reports... there were other kinds of collaboration as the Discovery Projects learned from the Foundation Projects (in our case directly as we absorbed and developed the insights from Heritage Connector in addition to learning from several others, especially Locating a National Collection). We were also in dialogue with the SPF1 project Living with Machines, with whom we shared historical interests and one staff member. But cross-Discovery Project collaboration proved difficult. Because the AHRC funded the five Discovery Projects as conventional research projects

⁵⁹ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

(with separate aims, objectives and research questions) the scheme lacked the inbuilt mechanisms to compel collaboration, and the separate delivery timetables meant that attempts at collaboration – which Congruence Engine promoted on several occasions – proved impossible to fulfil. There were commonalities of technique and concerns (as well as differing areas of focus) and so synthesis is possible, and we strongly encourage this to be undertaken as a next stage in the ambitions for the work that needs to be done.'

Arguably, the TaNC project participants are a 'community' at the forefront of digital collections research. Many evaluation participants felt the programme had built legacy, for example:

'And I think that's where the momentum issue is really important as well, because coming, as our project comes to an end, people are now buzzing with ideas about what they can do with this data and are looking for routes to take that forward and carry that work on and build on it. So, so, I think it really has, across the programme, demonstrated what the potential for this kind of work is and built enthusiasm and a cohort of people with new skills and new interests and finding ways to support that in future.' [Discovery participant]

'And what I've been really, really, what I've really noticed from the feedback of so many meetings where we've talked about impact of, on paths and the legacy in the future is the cross organizational discussions that are going to spin out of this and the value of the connect and connections that have been made across the consortium. And it's really one of the benefits of having a large consortium is that so many people met and worked quite closely with other people and they've generated quite good, well in some cases, very good connections, which I think will last be well beyond the project and take us into new places.' [Discovery participant]

One Discovery Project participant explained how their project represented the collaborative efforts that will be necessary towards achieving any shared vision:

'I don't think the national collection will be delivered by individual large organizations. I think it will be delivered by consortia. And so, I think the, it's really important to try or run that. And it was a really good opportunity to bring together some very varied research cultures in a single space and see where that led us. So, you know, kind of like trying to understand how each other operate was, was a thing and, and we had just a microcosm of, I think, what's going to come.' [Discovery participant]

6.5 Provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward

In the GLAM sector survey 2, 33% agreed that TaNC had provided clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward while 20% disagreed and around half (47%) said they 'don't know' if TaNC achieved this. This indicates progress compared to GLAM sector survey 1, which could have resulted from more showcasing of TaNC's projects in the meantime.

There was evidence at the interim evaluation stage that TaNC projects were being used as the basis for further funding applications. Engagement session participants all felt their project had some sort of impact

or utility that supports more funding. Many mentioned parts of their projects that are still resourced in some form, beyond the period of TaNC project funding. Others noted that they were actively seeking funding with collaborators they had met through TaNC. All were confident that TaNC demonstrated the need for funding and further investment in digital developments. A few participants pointed out that these developments, and the money to support them, is found at the international-level, and with international collaborations.

At the final evaluation stage, it was clear that Discovery Projects had made great efforts to share their learnings throughout their projects, through publications of different formats, including presentations, exhibitions and more. For example, Congruence Engine's final report detailed:⁶⁰

'We published a special issue of the (open access, online) Science Museum Group Journal after a year. We aim to publish two open access books in early 2026: the 18-chapter Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections from the Congruence Engine Project (UCL Press) and The UK Digital Collection: A Manifesto (University of London Press). Other papers are appearing in specialist journals. Our blog, with its 22 posts, has provided a window on the project's key concepts and developments. Team members spoke at digital humanities and history of science conferences and took part in TaNC webinars and in the programme's final Manchester conference. Our project's own final conference, joint with the annual Artefacts Consortium conference (of researchers associated with science museums worldwide), put the project's achievements before a deeply interested core global audience. We have established a GitHub repository for data and code and will devote a section of the Science Museum Group British Library-hosted data repository to key documents and outputs from the project. We produced two exhibits: the first, at the Discovery Museum in Newcastle, aimed to show the ambitions of the project via four short films. The second, a fully interactive digital exhibit which will run at the Science and Media Museum in Bradford from early 2025, makes accessible a huge number of heritage items within a map-based interactive that also reveals some of the digital tools we have used. In addition to the four exhibit films, Common Films have produced Bradford Forwards and Backwards, a 25-minute film inspired by the project, showcasing links between Bradford mills and textiles work in this post-industrial city.'

And for UNPATH'd Waters:⁶¹

'To make sure this project has a lasting impact, we have published all our methods, outputs, code and research so anyone can use it in their work and help the future of UK maritime heritage.'

At the overarching programme level, TaNC commissioned Alma Economics to estimate the Total Economic Value of a future unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets in the UK.⁶² The Programme Directorate

⁶⁰ Boon, Tim, Butterworth, Alex, Graham, Helen, Rees, Arran, Sichani, Anna-Maria, Belteki, Daniel, Fitzpatrick, Alex, & Winters, Jane. (2025). Final Report - Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14770779>

⁶¹ Sloane, Barney & Unpath'd Waters Consortium. (2025). Final Report - Unpath'd Waters: Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK. Towards a National Collection <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14888571>

⁶² Alma Economics (2024) Towards a National Collection: Total Economic Value of a unified digital collection. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12755041>

explained this would be used to feed into the ‘business case for funding a UK digital collections infrastructure.’ Contingent valuation methods were designed and data collected through surveys of the general population; academics and researchers and individuals with ‘special’ interest in cultural heritage (through referrals from cultural heritage organisations). Full findings are available in the published report. To summarise:

- For the public, average willingness to pay (in terms of an increase in annual taxes) of around £8 per person to support the development, maintenance and free accessibility of a unified digital collection of cultural heritage assets for the UK.
- For the academics and researchers, an average willingness to pay for the proposed service (in terms of a monthly subscription to access the service) of around £13 per person per month.
- For specialist interest individuals, an average willingness to pay for the service (in terms of a monthly subscription to access the service) of around £3 per person per month.
- The surveys indicated that reasons to value the service included use value and existence value.
- Zero valuations were given on the basis of not seeing the usefulness for themselves or others, or in the case of those who would use, objecting to the notion of them paying rather than accessing for free.

The report of Total Economic Value of a Unified Digital Collection contains findings which could be used to evidence the value of a unified digital collection from the perspective of these three types of potential beneficiaries, in monetary terms. It also highlights that the value placed on this is related to their direct use, or the assurance that others in society are directly using or benefitting. As such, the learnings from TaNC on ways to maximise benefits for a diverse range of audiences (see section 5.4) are crucial to couple with the contingent valuation monetary estimates.

6.6 Conclusion

This findings chapter includes findings on TaNC’s impact towards the digital collections research ecosystem.

In terms of TaNC’s benefits reaching across the UK, this was evidenced by the number of organisations based in different UK locations. Due to the set up with IROs and HEIs, these were consequently based in large population centres. There were clearly efforts to include organisations and people based in as many parts of the UK as possible.

Collaboration across geographies, types and sizes of organisations was described as valuable but challenging. Evaluation participants reflected that having large numbers of partners may look good on paper, but in practice, takes resource to ensure all are involved meaningfully in a project.

Certainly, learnings from TaNC were seen as useful to inform a shared vision for a national collection and to decide on future priorities and practical next steps (see chapter 8 for future priorities). There was a sense of a growing community given TaNC had brought skills, resource and capacity into HEIs and IROs in particular. Parity for the wider GLAM sector was seen as important, by HEIs and IROs, based upon their observations that some wider project partners brought more towards TaNC projects than they gained in the short-term.

Another objective of TaNC was to advance the case for enhanced funding. TaNC has resulted in many examples to build upon. An important factor for success is the strong motivation and work of all TaNC

projects to share their findings.⁶³ Discovery Projects produced prolific outputs for different audiences such as websites, films, articles, case studies and reports. Furthermore, TaNC can leverage commissioned reports such as the Total Economic Value of a Unified Digital Collection.⁶⁴

Chapter seven highlights key considerations raised by evaluation participants regarding TaNC's aims and objectives, and feedback on the TaNC programme.

⁶³ [Projects | Towards a National Collection](#)

⁶⁴ Alma Economics (2024) Towards a National Collection: Total Economic Value of a unified digital collection. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12755041>

7. Participant Feedback and Suggestions

7.1 Introduction

This chapter contains participant feedback and suggestions for beyond TaNC. The feedback is largely informed by insights shared during evaluation sessions with Discovery Projects and their final project reports.

The evaluators have grouped participants' feedback on the TaNC programme into 5 categories:

- Aims and objectives (see section 2.2 for context).
- Governance and accountability.
- Funding, costing and resourcing of projects (see section 2.1 for context).
- Bringing projects together (see section 2.4 for context).
- Policy recommendations.

Along with the prior findings chapters, this chapter is designed to:

- Prompt discussions on learning and improvement for future programmes.
- Inform UKRI.
- Provide those involved in the set up and delivery of any future initiatives with valuable suggestions.

7.2 TaNC's objectives and aim

In the GLAM sector surveys, respondents were asked about how important they considered TaNC's objectives to be, assigning an importance rating for each (see figure 7.1). 114 people gave a response to this question in GLAM survey 2, including a minority responding 'don't know'.

In terms of importance, the highest importance rating given in GLAM survey 2 was for 'benefiting a diverse range of audiences'; 96% selected 'very important' or 'slightly important'.

Results for GLAM survey 1 and GLAM survey 2 demonstrate very strong and sustained support from the cultural heritage sector towards the objectives of TaNC. Indeed, over three quarters of respondents agreed that each objective was important.

Figure 7.1: How important do you consider the following for the UK's GLAM sector?

In the sector surveys, a question was included to gauge the extent of agreement that TaNC had achieved its objectives, rating each objective. 110 people responded to this question in GLAM survey 2.

Approximately half of GLAM survey 2 respondents selected 'don't know' (45%-50%) as an answer response for questions asking about TaNC achieving its objectives (see figure 7.2a). This range was similar to those selecting don't know options for GLAM survey 1 in Summer 2023 (47%-54%).

Excluding the 'don't know' responses indicates perceived performance of TaNC towards its objectives (see figure 7.2b).

The perception was that TaNC had most room for improvement in 'benefitting a diverse range of audiences'; of those with an opinion, a majority disagreed that TaNC had achieved this objective, with 54% of respondents selecting 'slightly disagree' or 'strongly disagree' in GLAM survey 1 and 52% of respondents indicated the same in GLAM survey 2 (see section 5.4 for further elaboration).

In contrast, around two thirds of respondents to GLAM survey 2 agreed that TaNC achieved its aims to extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location (65% of respondents selected 'slightly agree' or 'strongly agree'). This is a slight decrease from the 71% of respondents who said the same in GLAM survey 1.

Opening up of collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research was the objective most respondents believed had been achieved (66% either 'slightly agree' or 'strongly agree'). However, excluding the objective about audiences, all objectives received over 50% agreement that they had been achieved (see figure 7.2b).

Figure 7.2a: Would you agree or disagree that Towards a National Collection is achieving the following objectives? Including 'don't know' responses.

Figure 7.2b: Would you agree or disagree that Towards a National Collection is achieving the following objectives? Excluding 'don't know' responses.

7.3 Governance and accountability

In the engagement sessions with projects, one project gave feedback that they were unhappy with the governance and accountability of TaNC. They made suggestions for future programmes funded by UKRI/ HEI:

- Publish Terms of Reference for any Steering Committee.
- Ensure the UKRI resolution process is followed by programmes.
- Ensure neutrality in any conflict resolution between partners.

Some further feedback for TaNC's Programme Directorate was mentioned by more than one Discovery Project. They felt that:

- Reporting and meetings at a Programme level had not been sufficiently accounted for when TaNC issued guidance on TaNC projects. Participants felt that if this had been built into the structure of these projects more formally, this would have ensured more input.
- More notice should have been given for TaNC project input to key documents, so this could be built into work plans. A couple of participants had flagged inaccuracies in information about their project which had not been corrected before publication.
- Participants felt that TaNC's Programme Directorate had more understanding of IROs than HEIs, and more understanding of IROs than the wider GLAM sector partners.

7.4 Funding and resource of projects

Evaluation participants were largely complimentary that TaNC had secured UKRI funding, and then that their organisations had been successfully awarded TaNC project funding. For example, an employee of an IRO explained their motivation to get involved:

'To try to secure a very large grant to prove that independent research organizations were players in the, in the field of research councils. So it's quite important for us too, strategically, because we got our status as a, as an independent research organization some years back and it had some success, but nothing particularly large. This was an opportunity to see whether we could walk the walk as well as talk the talk, I suppose... and also wanted to help show how collaborating organizations who don't fit within that usual AHRC structure could hopefully add significantly to research as well.' [Discovery participant]

Despite publicity of the size of the overall TaNC budget, some of those directly involved in COVID-19 and Foundation Projects felt budgets were small for the volume of work each project required:

'I think the overall size of the budgets that were available didn't necessarily match the ambitions of the project, the ambition for the programme, the ambition for the individual projects.' [Foundation participant]

Discovery Projects expressed that more time would have been beneficial, given they were ambitious in their plans and had multiple workstreams and many partners involved, for example:

'And having been involved in several other kind of proposals in Europe etcetera, what seems to be the case with the cultural heritage sector of the arts humanities, typically the money spent on the, on the sector is not comparable with other sectors perhaps. And these you know 3 million projects seems to be a huge project for the sector. What really happens when you are going towards a proposal of that size, which sounds like a lot of money, you tend to be quite ambitious on the outputs of the project. And that basically then translates into the number of experts and people that you need to collaborate with, you need to bring together for a decent competitive proposal. And when you find yourself into that, into that situation, then it is start dealing with your time, your allocation. And this is how we ended up having some quite awkward allocation numbers, not realistic. And on top of that is the overheads. So it is not only the time that we put down as a cost, but it is also the overheads claimed by institutions. All in all, the, you know, the actual programme or the way that is funded, it seems that is inflated in certain areas and it is deflated into, into our time that we allocate. Because realistically, if every one of us goes back and say how much time really you spent on this and we translate that, yeah, we wouldn't be in a position to claim the money or to go for the money that we want initially. But you know, these are very prestigious projects.' [Discovery participant]

'I think the key thing, and it's still true, is before TaNC came along, there was never, there was never a grant of the size to enable you to do the work and the ambition which we did. The other thing I would say from an institutional perspective, the size of grant and the scale of the programme gives, this gives TaNC projects a profile within the cultural organisations which just having a normal research grant doesn't have.' [Discovery participant]

'They were big projects, very big projects to manage with a lot of money and the same time frame as often much smaller, three-year HRC funded projects. And one thing that it would be wonderful, from my perspective, if could be considered for future calls like this, would be a sort of 1 + 3 model, where you get a year upfront to get everything in place, get your data. You know, it might be a subset of the overall project team, but something that allows the full three years of a big project to, you know, to be going right from the start. They were so big and so unwieldy in many ways that constraining that within three years felt like a big ask to me.' [Discovery participant]

Several TaNC projects raised issues with the division of funding, which seemed to result from eligibility for UKRI funding:

'But the funding model for the likes of the [redacted] Trust and others are, first of all, they get hit by the full economic cost, 80% model. And then secondly, they're told there's no overheads...on the one hand, you're saying, "come on in, the water is lovely." And on the other hand, you're going, "Oh yes, you're going to have to work really hard for every penny. And in fact, you're going to have to work twice as hard as any of the other organizations to do the same amount of work," which just doesn't feel fair.' [Discovery participant]

These participants were anxious that experience of partnering within TaNC would deter GLAMs who were not IROs from getting involved in the future:

'We weren't allowed to call them co-investigators. But to all intents and purposes, that was, that was the status they had. And that's actually a deeper thing about the whole IRO setup, and it's not, it's not particular to this funding. In fact, in most, most AHRC funding, you're not allowed to give people Co-investigator like status if they don't have the IRO status. And that is in it an inequity. So you're not actually creating any extra capacity within the regional museums. It's just expected that you can take that work within your current work programme, which is tricky.' [Discovery participant]

All TaNC project participants taking part in the engagement sessions explained that they had put more time into their TaNC project than was accounted for on paper in their funding applications and their project plans. For example:

'It was meant to be a day a week, but I was spending double that. I was managing three people, coordinating the project and conducting a bit of the data work... it was a very rewarding project in terms of my research, but very intense in terms of workload and engagement... I think there's an interesting question about juggling your role as the fixer in your organisation to make it happen, as alongside actually contributing to the actual work of the project.' [Discovery participant]

This disparity between time costed and time given appeared more acute for:

- Discovery Projects than for Foundation and Covid-19 Projects, as they were larger and over longer time scales.
- Co-Investigators, some with only a few hours a week for TaNC, which was not sufficient.
- Projects without project managers, even if they had a project administrator.
- People working for IROs when colleagues working on TaNC left and were not replaced by their organisation.
- Projects where some people contributing were academics who had less flexible schedules due to field working commitments or teaching timetables.
- Projects experiencing challenges, for example, if one partner had a change of priorities or resource, other partners felt a knock-on-effect.

One early career researcher explained that this challenge applied to other projects they were delivering, not only TaNC Discovery:

'I mean, I think there's a lot that can be said about this, but the, I think the biggest challenge is, and I can say this because I'm on 4 projects right now from all different funding bodies and they're all do the same thing, there's a lot of extra meetings and things that are invented that could have been, some of which could have been foreseen.

And this goes back to the funding application. At the funding application stage, I, when you can foresee that you're going to have these extra meetings, they should be costed in from the beginning or we, we should be made aware of them so that they can be costed in.

And if that is for me, the thing that everything else is under my control, like I can, I can scale back my vision if it doesn't quite work with the timing. But when you, you're constantly asked to go to more and more meetings to find time for collaboration, which obviously we want, it's not that we don't want to be communicating. I think for me, that was the biggest challenge. And because I can see it

happening in every, with every single funding body, it's, it seems like it's a systemic problem.'
[Discovery participant]

7.5 Bringing projects together

Comments about the degree TaNC brought projects together were interspersed with context on the time available and the resource pressures on individuals involved in the projects, for example:

'I think we touched on the, the administrative burden that came with having the, the being part of the programme and the fact that none of us, and I think you'll probably get that from the other four Discovery Projects as well, if you haven't already, that none of us really kind of bargained on quite how many program meetings there might be and so on.

And it, I think I got the sense that it started off with quite an ambitious approach to interaction, including quite a few people from each project meeting up and so on.

But that seemed to, to sort of fade away and the, the mechanisms for keeping in contact with each other during the three years across the five projects weren't really there. And it's actually quite difficult to work that out because you've got five projects running simultaneously, each of which you might want to benefit from what the other one is, is learning.' [Discovery participant]

Many participants gave positive feedback on the efforts made by the Programme Directorate, even if they struggled with their capacity to take advantage, or this came quite late on in 2024. For example,

'I just didn't have it, didn't have the capacity to think about organising yet another meeting and trying to like find a time that works for everyone. So, and I know that it's like half of what the Programme Team was doing within the project, but it did need that, that overall leadership to, to organise knowledge exchange doesn't just happen. It needs to be organised and it needs to have the leadership in place to, to recognise that some, that importance and also make those opportunities available for everyone. Because I know that there's probably other opportunities that might have come across and maybe they just weren't communicated, didn't, the communications didn't trickle down to all our project partners for whatever reason.' [Discovery participant]

'This kind of cross fertilisation or cross communication between the, between the different Discovery Projects. And I know the efforts were made, were made to do that. All the barriers to that I agree with. But I, but I will say that, actually, I discovered a huge amount about potential crossovers between projects in Manchester at a conference.' [Discovery participant]

There were mixed views on how well the Programme Directorate spotted common themes and challenges amongst projects. Some acknowledged these were spotted and then addressed through commissioned reports. However, the lag time was seen as an issue by Discovery Projects who would have benefitted from

this knowledge earlier on. An example given in several different engagement sessions was the topic of ethics. In this case, the report was praised but seen as coming too late with its publication in 2024.⁶⁵

One participant suggested that for future funding of programmes, a core work stream on these common thematic issues would be beneficial:

'I think that in the future that would be, that should be a kind of core work stream that checks in, like, or kind of has, if not oversight, then there's feeding into work that's across the teams as well.'
[Discovery participant]

7.6 Policy recommendations

Launched at the second conference, TaNC produced ten policy recommendations in order to build a UK digital collection:⁶⁶

Evaluation sessions held after the launch of these recommendations asked for feedback. Views expressed were that there was nothing to disagree with in the recommendations. However, many felt they were quite obvious and even out of step with the learnings coming from TaNC, for example:

"It feels like it didn't include anything that couldn't have been said five or more years ago. It doesn't reflect what has been learned by the TaNC projects and then the "so what?" across them.' [Discovery participant]

7.6 Conclusion

This chapter includes project participant feedback. Unlike at the interim evaluation stage, this feedback cannot feed into ongoing improvements to the programme. However, feedback and suggestions should inform set up and management of other UKRI programmes and any future programmes involving HEIs and the GLAM sector.

Results for GLAM survey 1 and GLAM survey 2 demonstrate very strong and sustained support from the cultural heritage sector on the objectives of TaNC. They also showed the highest level of importance was assigned to the objective of 'benefitting a diverse range of audiences'. Also, albeit based on a small sub-sample of individuals involved in projects, that this objective had most room for TaNC to improve.

Furthermore, feedback and suggestions were given on TaNC's governance and accountability, funding and resourcing of projects, success at bringing disparate projects together, and policy recommendations published at the end of 2024.

The overall Discovery Project budgets were not criticised per se, but evaluation participants reflected that the more partners, the further the money had to stretch. Furthermore, they fed back concerns about the

⁶⁵ Rutherford, Ananda; Sichani, Anna-Maria; Foxton, Katrina & Perry, Sara (2024). Ethics as Practice: Report on the 1st Discovery Project Ethics Workshop. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683142>

⁶⁶ Bailey, Rebecca, Pereda, Javier, Michaels, Chris, & Callahan, Tom. (2024). Unlocking the Potential of Digital Collections. A call to action. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838916>

distribution of funding within projects and the discrepancy between time costed in project bids and the time given by individuals towards projects.

Chapter eight focuses on recommendations for future priorities, taken from various sources consulted for this evaluation.

8. Future Investment

8.1 Introduction

This final chapter focuses on findings to inform future priorities. This brings together the desires expressed in published reports and the primary research conducted towards the evaluation. This chapter is intended to be of value to those involved in learning lessons, building on successes and maximising the legacy of TaNC.

Technical recommendations have not been included in this chapter of the evaluation report. As all Discovery Projects cited their recommendations sections in their final reports as the best ‘jumping-off point’ for deciding priorities for future investment, these have been extracted from each report and included verbatim in Appendix G.

8.2 Priorities for future investment

This section includes a compilation of data throughout the evaluation, which points to priorities for future investment. Firstly, this section explores the results of the GLAM surveys, before turning to additional context on these results from the evaluation engagement sessions.

GLAM survey results

The cultural heritage sector survey asked respondents to rank four priorities for future investment, from most important to least important (see figure 7.3). Interestingly, the order of priorities was the same in GLAM survey 2 (winter 2024/2025) as in GLAM survey 1 (summer 2023). From highest importance to lowest:

1. Training and support for digital skills.
2. Increased digitisation.
3. A source of technical development and expertise.
4. Guidance on copyright, licensing and open access.

The cultural heritage sector survey later asked respondents to rate the importance of four desires for future digital infrastructure in their sector, from most important to least important (see figure 7.4). Again, the order of priorities was the same in GLAM survey 2 as in GLAM survey 1. From highest importance to lowest:

1. Connect and cross-search data from different institutions.
2. Open multiple collections to current computational research tools.
3. Support the decolonisation of collections.
4. Enable citizen science such as crowdsourcing research.

Figure 7.3: What are your priorities for future investment?

Figure 7.4: What do you want a future digital infrastructure to do for the sector?

Training and support for digital skills

As detailed in previous sections (see 4.2, 4.3 and 4.4), evaluation participants expressed concerns around capacity, capability and skills within the GLAM sector.

The evaluation also brought perspectives from HEIs. TaNC projects competed for people with specialist computational skills (see 6.3). Overall, people who could bring hybrid skills or work well with others with skills in other specialisms were valued within TaNC. However, it was observed that job roles can be more restrictive than encouraged by programmes such as TaNC:

'Obviously the Research Council is very keen on people working in interdisciplinary way, but I think sometimes jobs are probably much more disciplinary focused. On the one hand, the job market required people to be very specialised in the fields, and on the other, funding streams like TaNC requesting interdisciplinary skills from researchers and academics and IROs, etcetera.' [Discovery participant]

One quote from the engagement sessions provides a suggestion on how to pool skills which relate to 'a source of technical development and expertise':

'I think some huge, huge national investment that doesn't sit within any one institutional organization and is open to all kinds of disciplines and people from any kind of research organization to come and spend time there. So, I'm thinking like a, an infrastructure equivalent to CERN, you know, the Large Hadron Collider, where people go and do a period of time there as part of their job or can apply for it, so that we can focus together on building the same thing, so we're not all reinventing the wheel. And a huge focus on standards because many elements of what we're doing are already being addressed elsewhere in the community. And the tricksiness about it is, is turning it from a project into a service. So, we need some joined up thinking around that. Let's not reinvent the wheel, let's just use what's out there already, and if it isn't fit for purpose, that's what these projects will have highlighted. So, let's put a huge amount of effort into that joint, communal, global effort. Often global. Yeah, there we are - loads of money, please.' [Foundation participant]

Increased digitisation

In the sector surveys, the GLAM sector took pains to point out differences between cataloguing and digitisation. For example, two different respondents to GLAM survey 2 explained:

'Cataloguing manuscript collections through cross-collection collaboration and the establishment of shared guidelines in order to ensure the consistency and comparability of descriptive metadata. Digitisation as an accompaniment to this is welcome, however it is very expensive and diverts resources away from cataloguing, and has a tendency to focus on 'treasures' and high profile items, which have already benefited disproportionately from research, cataloguing and facsimile production.'

'Digitisation of collections records and cataloguing are not the same thing... Digitisation has leap-frogged the hard work of good quality documentation and cataloguing meaning very poor quality records are freely circulating online and now being used to train AI - badly... bad information about

collections online because of a misplaced fervour that doing so automatically increases access to diverse audiences. It doesn't. Good quality digital collections information still needs mediating for users to get the most out of it.'

Concern was expressed that much is 'hidden' from public access:

'The real crisis is the enormous backlog of uncatalogued collections that cannot be surfaced to users through these channels due to the need for the basic cataloguing work which is required to attend to their security, content sensitivity, preservation, usability, and discoverability, needs.'

A number of GLAM respondents expressed frustrations with addressing the backlogs in collections records, let alone collections digitisation. For example, in GLAM survey 2:

'It would be helpful if research councils could instigate a meaningful fund to support collection processing work to which professional GLAM staff responsible for such collections could apply. This may not be exciting on the face of it, but would be transformative in terms of starting to open up access to collections for research and for the wider public benefit, and would lift the spirits of many HE archivists who are increasingly demoralised by the large and growing backlogs which they feel powerless to address.'

An alternative perspective expressed in the sector surveys was how GLAM accessioning policies had brought fundamental issues with collections management, and collections records management, over the long-term:

'The GLAM sector has collected more than it can afford to manage responsibly over many decades, and the research infrastructure required to deliver on the promise of these collections must entail some investment in efficient collection processing at the institutions responsible for the materials.'

A point of contention was revealed in GLAM survey 1 on open access. Some responses called for its extension and safeguarding. Others touched on open access having negative repercussions for organisations, including lost income. GLAM survey 2 contained many calls for open access, which could indicate a growing appetite and pressure for open access steps from within GLAM survey 2. For example, one respondent explained that they desired:

'The ability to share use and reuse collections data and metadata free from restrictive licensing or 'ownership' - ensuring that the digital infrastructure remains community-owned and governed and free from commercial takeover.'

In GLAM survey 2, there were several references to the move to digital-born heritage:

'Put less emphasis on digitisation. More emphasis on born-digital infrastructure. There is a digital dark age c.1980-2030 that most public GLAMs are not addressing.'

Guidance on copyright, licensing and open access

As highlighted earlier (see chapter 5.2) sharing collections are affected by licensing and access in place and rules applied to new records.

Evaluation participants were supportive of more guidance in this area, but also of more progressive approaches, for example:

'I think a really intelligent piece of research on how we get to Open Access and get past paywalls and licensing, because they're right in the way of this. And then I think, there must protect intellectual ownership and control without, without stifling the release of the some of the information for research.' [Discovery participant]

'A current consistent approach to data and rights management is really fundamental, but also massively thorny, thorough, massively thorny issue. And so, that's you, you know, you can see we want to do that, but really we need intervention at some, you know, supreme level to make that happen.' [Discovery participant]

8.3 Value from future investment

For those who did support funding towards a national collection digital infrastructure, there were three main asks for funding approaches. Firstly, they expressed that funding should be directed to build on what has been developed, and lessons learnt from programmes and projects including TaNC. Evaluation participants raised the large investment from TaNC itself, and the need for value for money:

'Any truly national infrastructure would need to be useful to institutions of all sizes and funding models. There are examples of this - for metadata aggregation, TNA Discovery and Archives Hub spring to mind. Why not invest more to upgrade core services with a proven track record?' [Discovery participant]

Secondly, they were conscious that any future investment should be considerate of environmental impacts. Thirdly, that funding must develop solutions which can make a difference to the wider GLAM sector, not limited to larger, national organisations:

'This all sounds very metropolitan/big institution and big city focused. How does this impact, support, enable smaller institutions? Need to start with a 'what's the problem or opportunity', then move to the solution. All too often, 'digital' is being promoted as an answer ,but it's not clear what problem it's actually solving. So, need to be very clear on audience, visitor, and user expectations, the trends shaping these, and where and how institutions can best invest. For the independent museum I'm involved in, for instance, digitising collections has been expensive in terms of staff time, even when supported by grants, and for little return. Definitely want smaller organisations to be part of this and benefit from it though.' [Discovery participant]

8.4 Inclusivity of future investment

Participants from the large organisations in the GLAM sector surveys and engagement sessions desired developments, and investment, that were inclusive of smaller organisations. Therefore, organisations who do not have IRO status, nor are funded directly by governments, should be given a place at the table in any conversations about what happens beyond the TaNC programme.

Evaluation participants often believed that any digital infrastructure should be designed inclusively, with the whole GLAM sector in mind:

'Actually, this is a piece of infrastructure that should be funded that will enable individual museums [to] pull their data together in places, where there is a specialised place that can then push it outwards.

And this kind of Federated kind of approach, distributed model, where you're not throwing everything in one bag. I think that kind of those, those are the real core pieces of work that needed to happen now to enable more of the interesting research projects like what TaNC has produced to happen on a more regular basis.' [Discovery participant]

8.5 Risks of future investment

Evaluation participants brought up risks associated with some of the technologies employed towards digital infrastructure, for example:

'It's really difficult at the moment and we need to, we need to have a real programme of ethical discussion, because on the one hand machine learning techniques carry a huge number of moral difficulties, I think. And our data are also ethically difficult. But also if, I mean, as in every other sector, if AI is going to have a big impact on the work that's done, then there are all sorts of risks to future work which also need to be understood.' [Discovery participant]

Indeed, the evaluation findings show that future investment must carefully consider which collections and whose collections are included within a 'national collection' or any form of data linkage.

8.6 Sustainability of future investment

Responses from the GLAM sector surveys showed concerns about the funding sustainability of the sector. There were many pleas for funding and anxiety expressed about the security of roles within the sector. One respondent summed up these feelings:

'We need sustained funding for core infrastructure and staffing, and neglected services need additional funds to make up for years of austerity.'

GLAM survey respondents explained thinking and funding are too short-term considering digital developments:

'Far too many funding streams and projects are short term and only last as long as the funding does. TaNC is a great idea but I am sceptical about its long term utility.'

Discovery Projects felt that systems change takes long-term, sustained investment, rather than short-term programmes and projects. For example,

'I think they're [TaNC projects] really good and transformative. The issue we've got is the longitudinal nature of them. And that's not just in the classic, "we want more", but I think if UKRI or particularly the AHRC could look maybe more to the EPSIC sort of programme grant style model, where you're looking at sort of funding over a decade, old type. I think your ability to deliver on some of these things would be good, because we slightly have a habit of creating links to community

groups and setting them up and putting support networks in place, and then dropping them.'
[Discovery participant]

Lastly, evaluation participants explained how whatever is created in terms of solutions must be fit for purpose and continue to be well managed:

'What, perhaps, I would love to see, you know, happening in the future is to have, together with the idea of the national collection, the national infrastructure that we can somehow add there, you know, some repositories, some ways to access digital hosting, something that we can be centrally, all. A model, perhaps, that can allow us to engage with cloud computing with everything. Because it seems to me that the vision, it is a long-term vision, it is a community-based vision, etcetera. But the running of the model is pretty business oriented. And certainly, you know, once the money runs out, then the vision shuts down. And I think we need, we need a way to breach that, because we cannot have a vision without a very sustainable business plan at the end of the day.'
[Discovery participant]

8.7 Conclusion

GLAM sector surveys revealed, the order of priorities for future investment from highest importance to lowest:

1. Training and support for digital skills
2. Increased digitisation
3. A source of technical development and expertise
4. Guidance on copyright, licensing and open access

In the sector surveys, the GLAM sector took pains to point out differences between cataloguing and digitisation. They highlighted digital-born collections in addition to digitisation of analogue collections. GLAM sector workers expressed concern that collections were not publicly accessible, including in the digital sphere, and welcomed resource to improve cataloguing and digitisation backlogs.

Evaluation participants were supportive of training and support for digital skills, but aware of challenges within the GLAM and HEI sectors.

In all cases, evaluation participants were actively thinking about how to create shared resources to help the wider GLAM sector, such as skills hubs, digital repositories and more.

Reflections from evaluation participants are included on:

- Value from future investment.
- Inclusivity of future investment.
- Risks of future investment.
- Sustainability of future investment.

The final reports of the Discovery Projects provide a more comprehensive account of technical and non-technical recommendations resulting from each.

Appendix A: Programme Evaluation Theory of Change Model

Appendix B: Reference List for Desk Research

Commissioned Reports and Resources

Alma Economics (2024) Towards a National Collection: Total Economic Value of a unified digital collection. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12755041>

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Pereda, Javier. (2024) Getting Ready for a Digital Future. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11394465>

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Discovery Projects Additional Outputs

Boon, Tim, Winters, Jane, & Rees, Arran (2024) The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13379469>

Appendix C: Engagement Sessions Discussion Guides

For the Discussion Guide, version May 2023 used for Foundation, and COVID-19 Projects please see Appendix C of [Interim Evaluation Report](#).

Discussion Guide, v. November 2024

*indicates change of wording from version May 2023

Note this is the core discussion guide for engagement sessions with people involved in Discovery Projects.

Note the participants will have received- privacy notice, and information in advance.

Key- Grey- prioritise

Set up

Introduce Diffley Partnership Team

As you know, we are contracted as evaluators of the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) Programme.

Welcome to the engagement session–

- Explain the discussion will last up to 2 hours, including a break in the middle.
- This time will incorporate time for discussion and a participatory exercise
- There will be plenty of time to get your views across and discuss issues between yourselves, something we encourage; my role is to keep the conversation flowing, ensuring we cover the broad areas we need to and ask any follow-up questions,
- Fully anonymous and confidential; The Diffley Partnership abide by the Market Research Society Code of Practice and the SRA Ethical Guidelines.
- Request permission to record discussion – with your permission I will record the discussion; this is just so we can go back and listen again after the discussion.
- The recording will not be shared with the Programme Directorate, and we will delete the recording when our analysis is complete.

Do you have any questions before we start?

Background and introduction TaNC

Please tell us your role and how you were involved in TaNC- which project?

When did everyone here get involved with TaNC? Was it from project application, at the start of the projects or later on?

What were your main motivations for getting involved in TaNC?

How did TaNC feature in your day to day?

Prompt- heavily involved, on the periphery

Prompt- single or multiple TaNC projects

Prompt- other complimentary work during this time

Prompt- working with colleagues on TaNC/ working with people in other organisations on TaNC/ engaging with TaNC programme staff

Do you have any thoughts or feedback on the funding model?

Prompt- participation of diverse range of organisations

TaNC objectives

What does 'a national collection' mean to you?

Prompt- feeling, associations, degree of support

I'm going to turn to TaNC's objectives and ask for your views on those. We really welcome your thoughts and discussion.

FACILITATOR SHARES SLIDE/ CHAT WITH EACH OBJECTIVE

Begin to dissolve barriers between collections

Extend researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location,

Be active and of benefit across the UK,

Open up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research

Benefit a diverse range of audiences,

Provide clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward

Do you think this objective is important? Why/ why not?

What progress do you think the TaNC projects you were involved with made towards achieving this?

What progress do you think the TaNC programme overall has made towards achieving this?

What challenges did you experience through TaNC?

PROMPT: COVID-19, Brexit, Economic conditions, Technology limitations

FOLLOW UP: How did that impact your project and its outcomes?

What opportunities did you find through TaNC?

PROMPT: TaNC governance, in-kind contributions from participating institutions, technology developments, knowledge exchange, social media engagement

FOLLOW UP: How did that impact your project and its outcomes?

Project reflections relevant for the Programme evaluation

How do you think TaNC is contributing to creation of job opportunities?

FOLLOW UP: Any examples from TaNC project?

How do you think TaNC is contributing to skills development opportunities?

FOLLOW UP: Any examples from TaNC project?

In what ways do you think TaNC is enhancing the reputation of UK's GLAM sector?

FOLLOW UP: Any examples from TaNC project?

How do you think TaNC is contributing to skills development opportunities?*

FOLLOW UP: Support for early career researchers, e.g. study trips, exchanges, conferences?

FOLLOW UP: Any examples from TaNC project?

In what ways do you think TaNC is embedding Equalities Diversity and Inclusion agendas?

FOLLOW UP: Any examples from TaNC project?

Collaboration

We are keen to hear your views on TaNC enabling an effective collaborative environment.

Do you have any examples of the following?

- New relationships between organisations, cross-disciplines and orgs with the public
- Productive partnerships
- Addressing siloed working
- Cross-disciplinary working
- Working between HEI researchers and GLAM professionals

What challenges did you experience in terms of collaboration?*

PROMPT: How were these overcome?

What would you advise to encourage meaningful collaboration? –

PROMPT- approaches, mechanisms, support

Future Focus

To what extent would you agree or disagree with these statements?

- TaNc is transforming digital search
- TaNC is transforming digital research capability
- TaNC is transforming public engagement

- TaNC has produced innovation?

FACILITATOR TO ADD INTO ZOOM CHAT

FOLLOW UP: Why do you agree or disagree?

FOLLOW UP: Do you have any suggestions?

In November at the conference, TaNC launched a policy recommendation document. I'm going to ask you what you think of its recommendation on what should be done to build a UK digital collection. *

I'll share a few at a time and then ask you for your thoughts in general.

FACILITATOR TO ADD INTO ZOOM CHAT

To build a UK digital collection, we need to:

1. Selection

Broaden our approach to what we include in our digital collections and expand who participates with the process of creating them.

2. Production

Accelerate how data is produced and allow new technologies to accelerate its enrichment

3. Skills

Build upon the skills in data creation already within digital collections organisations through a scalable, sustainable approach to accessing advanced technology skills

4. Reuse and rights management

Adopt a coherent, consistent approach to data and rights management

5. Access and engagement

Make the platforms and infrastructure through which digital collections are used and accessible to everyone

6. Security

Ensure our data and technology infrastructure, and the way they are used, are protected by common standards and legislation, as governed by good practice

7. Preservation

Take a long-term view on the preservation of data to ensure we can access it despite forces of change

8. Impact

Understand how our digital collections are used so we can fully harness their cultural, social and economic value

9. Models and framework

Treat digital collections as first-class research objects that allow us to transform our understanding of collections and the world

10. Experimentation

Continuously expose these collections to new technologies and new ways of thinking, while prioritising research into their environmental impact

Looking to the future, how is UK digital collections research infrastructure best improved?

Having participated in a TaNC project, what do you think should be a priority for future funding?*

How would you build a compelling case for funding beyond the current five year TaNC programme?- any recommendations for the TaNC team?*

Conclusions and wrap-up

Thank you very much for the discussion, is there anything not already covered that you would like to mention?

Appendix D: TaNC Projects

Foundation Projects			
Project Name	Duration	Involved Organisations	Web presence
Heritage Connector	February 2020-December 2021	Science Museum Group University of London Victoria and Albert Museum (V&A)	Heritage Connector: Transforming text into data to extract meaning and make connections - Science Museum Group
Provisional Semantics	February 2020-February 2022	Tate Imperial War Museums National Trust University of the Arts London	Provisional Semantics Tate
Practical Applications of IIIF	February 2020-April 2022	The National Gallery British Library The National Portrait Gallery University of Edinburgh	TANC - IIIF - index (tanc-ahrc.github.io)
Persistent Identifiers	February 2020-January 2022	The British Library Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh University of Glasgow The National Gallery	Persistent Identifiers GitHub Page

Deep Discoveries	February 2020- July 2021	The National Archives University of Surrey Victoria & Albert Museum Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh	Deep Discoveries GitHub page
Engaging Crowds	February 2020- April 2022	The National Archives University of Oxford Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh National Maritime Museum	TANC Engaging Crowds (tanc-ahrc.github.io)
Locating a National Collection	February 2020- July 2022	British Library University of Exeter The National Trust Historical Royal Palaces	Locating a National Collection - The British Library (bl.uk)
Preserving and Sharing Born Digital and Hybrid Objects	February 2020- March 2022	Victoria & Albert Museum (V&A) Birkbeck College British Film Institute	V&A · Preserving And Sharing Born Digital And Hybrid Objects (vam.ac.uk)
Covid-19 Projects			
Project Name	Duration	Involved Organisations	Web presence
Digital Footprints and Search Pathways: Working with National Collections in Scotland during COVID-19 Lockdown to Design Future Online Provision	April 2021- March 2022	University of Strathclyde University of Edinburgh National Museums Scotland National Galleries of Scotland	Digital Footprints – Working with national collections in Scotland during the Covid-19 lockdown to design future online provision (strath.ac.uk)

Making it FAIR: Understanding the Lockdown 'Digital Divide' and the Implications for the Development of UK Digital Infrastructures	January 2021- November 2021	University of York Museum of London Archaeology The Collections Trust Culture24 The Audience Agency Intelligent Heritage & Knowledge Integration	Making it FAIR
Visitor Interaction and Machine Curation in the Virtual Liverpool Biennial	January 2021- August 2021	University of Durham Liverpool John Moores University Liverpool Biennial	Visitor Interaction and Machine Curation in the Virtual Liverpool Biennial
Discovery Projects			
Project Name	Duration	Involved Organisations	Web presence
The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories	November 2021- January 2025	PI: Dr Timothy Boon, Science Museum Group Co-Is: Science Museum Group, British Film Institute, Historic Buildings and Monuments Commission for England, National Museums of Scotland, Universities of London, Leeds and Liverpool, University College London. Partner organisations: BBC History, Birmingham Museums Trust, Bradford Museums and Galleries, BT Heritage & Archives, Grace's Guide to Industrial History, Isis Bibliography of the History of Science, MadLab, The National Archives, National Museum Wales, National Museums of Northern Ireland, National Trust, Saltaire World Heritage Education Association, Society for the History of Technology, Tyne & Wear Archives & Museums (Discovery), Victoria and Albert Museum, Whipple Museum of the History of Science, Wikimedia UK.	The Congruence Engine

<p>Our Heritage, Our Stories: Linking and Searching Community-Generated Digital Content to Develop the People’s National Collection</p>	<p>October 2021-January 2025</p>	<p>PI: Professor Lorna Hughes, University of Glasgow Co-Is: Universities of Glasgow and Manchester, The National Archives Partner organisations: Tate, The British Museum, Association for Learning and Technology, Digital Preservation Coalition, Software Sustainability Institute, Archives+, Dictionaries of the Scots Language, National Lottery Heritage Fund, National Library of Scotland, National Library of Wales, Public Record Office of Northern Ireland & Wikimedia UK</p>	<p>Our Heritage, Our Stories</p>
<p>Transforming Collections: Reimagining Art, Nation and Heritage</p>	<p>November 2021-January 2025</p>	<p>PI: Professor susan pui san lok, University of the Arts London Co-Is: University of the Arts London, Tate, National Museums Scotland Partner organisations: Arts Council Collection, Art Fund, Art UK, Birmingham Museums Trust, British Council Collection, Contemporary Art Society, iniva (Institute of International Visual Art), JISC Archives Hub, Manchester Art Gallery, Middlesbrough Institute of Modern Art, National Museums Liverpool, Van Abbemuseum & Wellcome Collection.</p>	<p>Transforming Collections</p>
<p>The Sloane Lab: Looking Back to Build Future Shared Collections</p>	<p>October 2021-September 2024</p>	<p>PI: Professor Julianne Nyhan, University College London and TU Darmstadt Co-Is: University College London, The British Museum, & The Natural History Museum Partner organisations: British Library, Historic Environment Scotland, Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh, National Museums of Scotland, Archives and Records Association, Collecting the West project funded by the Australian Research Council, Down County Museum, National Galleries of Scotland, Oxford University Herbaria & metaphacts</p>	<p>Sloane Lab – Looking back to build future shared collections</p>

<p>Unpath'd Waters: Marine and Maritime Collections in the UK</p>	<p>October 2021- November 2024</p>	<p>PI: Mr Barney Sloane, Historic England</p> <p>Co-Is: Universities of Ulster, York, Southampton. Portsmouth, Bangor, Bradford, St Andrews; Glasgow School of Art, Historic Buildings and Monuments Commission for England, National Oceanography Centre, Historic Environment Scotland, Museum of London Archaeology, Royal Museums Greenwich</p> <p>Partner organisations: Royal Commission on the Ancient and Historical Monuments (Wales), Maritime Archaeology Trust, Nautical Archaeology Society, Mary Rose Trust, Wessex Archaeology, Manx National Heritage, Marine Management Organisation, Northern Ireland Department of Communities, Cadw, Lloyd's Register and Lloyd's Register Foundation, Protected Wrecks Association, British Geological Survey, UK Hydrographic Office</p>	<p>Unpath'd Waters</p>
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Appendix E: Research Participants- GLAM Survey 2 Respondents

Which of the following best describes your sector? n=134

- Museums and Galleries
- More than one of the type of organisation above
- Archives
- Libraries
- Historic Environment/Heritage
- None of the above

Where is your organisation based? n=127

Which of the following best describes your role? n=127

Does your role involve any of the following? Please tick all that apply to you

n=124

Appendix F: Sector Survey

Wider GLAM sector - Questionnaire 2 of 2

v. November 2024

For Questionnaire 1 of 2, v.15 June 2023, please see Appendix F of [Interim Evaluation Report](#).

*indicates change of wording from v.15 June 2023

Introduction

If you are an employee, volunteer, or student in the UK's Galleries Libraries Archives and Museums sector, we invite you to complete this survey. Your feedback is important for shaping the future of UK collections infrastructure and building a case for its future funding.

Historic Environment Scotland has commissioned independent researchers, Diffley Partnership, to conduct an evaluation of the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) programme. This programme takes place from 2020 to 2025 and includes sixteen research projects. More information on this programme can be found [here](#).

This survey asks about your familiarity with and thoughts on the Towards a National Collection programme. It also gives you the opportunity to share your views on the needs and future direction of the Galleries Libraries Archives and Museums (GLAM) sector. Survey results will be important for influencing future support from the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) in the GLAM sector.

We would be grateful if you could complete this short survey even if you are not familiar with Towards a National Collection (TaNC).

The survey will take no longer than 10 minutes to complete. Your response is entirely confidential and will not be seen outside of the Diffley Partnership research team. After the survey closes, Diffley Partnership will analyse findings and report overall trends back to Historic Environment Scotland. Our reporting will not identify any respondents. For our full privacy notice please visit this webpage.

If you have any questions about this survey, please contact Diffley Partnership at surveys@diffleypartnership.co.uk

Thank you in advance for your time and input.

About your role and organisation

Firstly, we ask a few questions about your work. These will help with our analysis and will not be used to identify you in reporting.

Q1.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ONE

Which of the following best describes your sector?

- Libraries
- Archives
- Museums and Galleries
- Historic Environment/Heritage
- More than one of the type of organisation above
- None of the above [IF YES TO JUST THIS ONE, EXCLUDE FROM SURVEY]

Q2.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ONE

Where is your organisation based?

- Northern Ireland
- Scotland
- Wales
- England
- Other (please specify)

Q3.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ONE

Which of the following best describes your role?

- Paid employee
- Volunteer
- Student/Trainee

Q4.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ALL

Does your role involve any of the following? Please tick all that apply to you

- [RANDOMISE ORDER]
- Digitisation and/or cataloguing
 - Research
 - Public access to collections
 - Public engagement

- Skills development within organisation
- Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
- Collaboration across collections
- Collaboration across sectors
- Collaboration with universities
- Digital collections research infrastructure
- Digital analytics
- None of the above
- Other – please describe

Familiarity with Towards a National Collection

The next few questions are about your interaction with the Towards a National Collection programme, please complete even if this survey is the first time you have heard of this programme.

Q5.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ONE

Before taking this survey, had you heard of Towards a National Collection?

Yes

No

IF Q5 = YES

Q6.

MANDATORY

SELECT ALL

Have you interacted with the Towards a National Collection through any of the following? Please tick all that apply to you.

[RANDOMISE ORDER]

Twitter

Youtube

Instagram

Attended 2023 conference on April 26th at the British Museum

Attended 2024 conference on November 20th at Contact Theatre, Manchester*

Through a JiscMail list

E-newsletter

Website

Attended a webinar

None of the above

Other – please describe

IF Q5 = YES

Q7.

ASK ALL

MANDATORY

SELECT ONE

Were* you involved with Towards a National Collection?

Yes, involved at the programme level and within at least one Towards a National Collection project

Yes, involved at the overall programme level

Yes, involved in multiple Towards a National Collection projects

Yes, involved in one Towards a National Collection project

No, I am not directly involved in the programme

IF Q7= YES options

Experience of Towards a National Collection

The next few questions are about your experience of the Towards a National Collection programme (TaNC).

Q.8

MANDATORY

Do you agree or disagree that TaNC has resulted in the following?:

Helped our organisation improve our digital policy and strategy

Helped our organisation improve our digital capacity and capability

Helped us improve digital search of collections records

Helped us develop collaborations with other organisations

Helped us improve working across different disciplines

Helped us develop partnerships with the higher education sector

Helped skills development within our organisation

Helped us engage with public audiences

Helped us be innovative

SCALE: Strongly agree, slightly agree, slightly disagree, strongly disagree, don't know

UK GLAM Sector and Digital Collections Developments

The last few questions ask about your views on the UK's Galleries Libraries Archives Museums and heritage sector, sometimes referred to as GLAMs.

Q.9

ASK ALL

How important do you consider the following for the UK's GLAM sector?

Dissolving barriers between collections

Extending researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location

Active and of benefit across the UK

Opening up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research

Benefiting a diverse range of audiences

Providing clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward

SCALE: very important, slightly important, slightly unimportant, very unimportant, don't know

Q.10

ASK ALL

Would you agree or disagree that Towards a National Collection achieved* the following objectives?

Dissolved* barriers between collections

Extended* researcher and public access beyond the physical boundaries of their location

Was* active and of benefit across the UK

Opened* up collections to new cross-disciplinary and cross-collection lines of research

Benefited* a diverse range of audiences

Provided* clear evidence and exemplars that support enhanced funding going forward

SCALE: Strongly agree, slightly agree, slightly disagree, strongly disagree, don't know

Q.11

ASK ALL

What are your priorities for future investment in the GLAM sector?

TEXT FIELD

Q.12

ASK ALL

What are your priorities for future investment? Please rank the following (where 1 is most important and 4 is least important):

RANDOMISE ORDER

Increased digitisation

Training and support for digital skills development

A source of technical development and expertise

Guidance on copyright, licensing and open access

SCALE:1,2,3,4

Q.13

ASK ALL

What do you want a future digital infrastructure to do for the sector? (where 1 is most important and 4 is least important):

RANDOMISE ORDER

Connect and cross-search data from different institutions
Enable citizen science such as crowdsourcing research
Open multiple collections to current computational research tools
Support the decolonisation of collections

SCALE:1,2,3,4

Q.14

ASK ALL

Is there anything else you want from future investment in digital collections infrastructure?

TEXT FIELD

Appendix G: Recommendations from Discovery Projects' End of Project Reports

Congruence Engine

Summary Recommendations

What

The 'UK digital collection' should be understood in practice to be a facilitative infrastructure for collections linkage ('UK collections linkage'), not a standalone digital collection.

How (by what means)

- Accessible Technical Infrastructure: We recommend the creation and maintenance of an accessible, open, technical infrastructure to enable participatory collections linkage using Linked Open Data (LOD) principles and via open data repositories.
- Heritage organisation datafication of collections to enable this linkage.
- People and skills: We recommend long-term government investment to ensure the continuity of digital, historical, curatorial, and hybrid skills in the GLAM sector.

How (in what manner)

- Social Machine: All stakeholders should accept that, although automation using digital technique is essential, it will be human motivation and action – both individual and institutional – that determines which collections and historical data are made linkable, and are linked.
- Anti-Oppressive Practice: UK collections linkage should embrace anti-oppressive practice as a guiding principle to mitigate perpetuation of harm, especially as encoded in GLAM collections data.
- Open Access Data: Data deriving from public sources should be created and retained, openly accessible in public repositories, without commercial paywalls, however its creation is funded.

Who

- Diversity of Action: We recommend that the creation of this infrastructure be undertaken by means of the enrolment of diverse heritage organisations, communities and people to create, curate and link collections and their data.
- Leadership should come from a coalition of senior figures in the heritage sector (perhaps led by NMDC), DCMS and UKRI, with IROC providing expertise.

- **Funding:** The research, digitisation/datafication and long-term implementation phases to this work each require bespoke funding from appropriate sources: UKRI, DCMS, MHLG, NHLF, trusts and foundations.

Full Recommendations

UK collections linkage has both social and digital components. It will rely strongly on people and the **care** they have for heritage, their **contributions** to making and maintaining heritage, and the **connections** forged through that work.

The collections to be linked are heterogenous in ownership (from national GLAMs via local authority to private museums, and private collections), scale (from millions of items to dozens) and medium (objects, documents, publications, records, visual and time-based media and records of historical places).

Building UK collections linkage is a substantial undertaking. In *Congruence Engine* we have been exploring, via the social machine metaphor, how this can be accomplished. Paying particular attention to how the social and technical might be combined, our recommendations for developing a united digital collection are as follows:

What

The ‘UK digital collection’ should be understood in practice to be a facilitative infrastructure for collections linkage (‘UK collections linkage’), not a standalone digital collection.

Following the TaNC mandate, our principal focus has been the liberation of large publicly owned collections, but the principles that apply there also apply across the whole ecosystem of heritage, stretching to the individual collector.

- The priority of heritage organisations, especially those that have invested in new storage for their reserve collections, is to make their physical collections intellectually accessible. Pooling data will be attractive to them insofar as it enhances the visibility and usability of their collections and enables them to conduct their core functions more effectively.
- GLAM custody of collections imposes the obligation of very long term record keeping, meaning that their interest is also in holding the primary digital record – however enriched – of the items in their care. Ready access to this data or either directly from the institutions, or through open distributed repositories via APIs, rather than wholesale duplication in a UK digital collection, should provide the way forward.

How (by what means)

The creation of UK collections linkage requires four categories of activity in overlapping phases:

- **Continuing research:** to create the needed scalable prototypes for a future infrastructure (large scale proof-of-concept, building on TaNC), the (digital) apps and user interfaces, and debate on the (ethical) frameworks to enable this. This may best continue on a project basis.

- Digitisation and datafication of collections to enable their linkage (rolling-out the necessary transformations and techniques across the GLAM sector). This should be enacted on a programme – not project – basis at the decade-length scale.
- Creation and readily availability of social historical datasets (‘connective tissue data’) for linkage, hosted in open repositories.
- Long-term implementation of linkage by a wide variety of organisations and people supported by techniques and frameworks developed in i, acting on data produced in ii and iii.

Accessible Technical Infrastructure: We recommend the creation and maintenance of an accessible, open, technical infrastructure to enable participatory collections linkage using Linked Open Data (LOD) principles and via open data repositories.

To be sustainable and useful, UK collections linkage must be accessible to everyone. We recommend:

- the creation and maintenance of simple, scalable, accessible, and open technical infrastructure – including a data registry and a resource index (for ontologies, thesauruses, gazetteers etc) – to enable participatory collections linkage.
- investment in resources, systems and services to enable more diverse engagement and contributions.

Data Infrastructure: UK collections linkage must be supported by a shared and open data infrastructure that organisations and individuals are able easily to access.

We recommend:

- Collections data should be transformed to adhere to shared standards and principles such as IIIF and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), learning from initiatives like OpenGLAM and Collections as Data.ⁱ
- Collections data should be published with licences that allow for further enhancements and its use as Linked Open Data on the model of, or using, shared and open platforms such as Wikidata and FreeCen.ⁱⁱ
- The GLAM digital backlog should be addressed by supporting programmes that produce machine-readable and interoperable data, though not necessarily full-scale cataloguing (as linked open data may reduce the need for this).
- A long-term funding strategy to avoid the privatisation of key public data assets and infrastructure.
- Long term funding for the Museum Data Service and similar services for the library and archive sector (potentially an aspect of the UK National Data Library)
- Provision of funding and technical support to GLAM organisations lacking specialist digital departments for the preparation of collections data.

Heritage organisations and other collection-holders should move to datafy their collections to enable this linkage. For each organisation, this will require:

- Thoughtful and careful selection of levels of record and other material to datafy. In the world of LOD, all data has value because it enhances linkage. Organisations will benefit from extending their item records by adding associated material from older catalogues, exhibition text, support files, etc.

- Extraction of terminology using Named Entity Recognition, Regular Expressions, OpenRefine and other programs, preparing data for later entity linkage.
- Selective catalogue enhancement, most likely with the help of human-overseen digital techniques, tightening of dates and identification of the associations and purposes of collections items.

People and skills: We recommend long-term investment to ensure the continuity of digital, historical, curatorial, and hybrid skills in the GLAM sector.

We recommend:

- UKRI, DCMS, MHLG and other major funders should support the development of career paths for long-term digital and hybrid roles in GLAM organisations.
- The provision of long-term or permanent roles for heritage data scientists within GLAM organisation to sustain and embed open collections data usage.
- Development of programmes to improve digital literacy and skills in smaller organisations and community groups to reduce barriers to contribution.
- Involvement of local heritage practitioners and small heritage organisations in paid capacities and with training programmes available.
- Employment of facilitators to build relationships, surface and negotiate knowledge systems and power structures, and support the (un)learning necessary to collaboratively build anti-oppressive collections-linking work.
- The salary discrepancy between the GLAM and private sector – especially with regard to the employment of people with data skills – be addressed and mitigated by offering stability, good work environments and interesting collaborative work to foster innovation and growth.

With regard to research projects:

- UKRI should issue further guidance on productive and realistic FTE time commitments for investigators.
- UKRI should require that larger projects are resourced with project managers, coordinators, and administrators for working across organisations.
- UKRI should consider organising future research programmes that have a common aim in such a way that expectations of cross-project collaboration are built-in and actionable.

How (in what manner)

Social Machine: All stakeholders should accept that, although automation using digital technique is essential, it will be human motivation and action – both individual and institutional – that determines which collections and historical data are made linkable, and are linked.

Congruence Engine has shared the experience of other practitioners in this field: that data creation, curation and linkage is an intensely human activity.ⁱⁱⁱ

We recommend:

- The promotion of social capital through an emphasis on the role of people within and beyond collection-holding heritage organisations.
- The coalition responsible for developing UK collections linkage should issue clear guidance on both social and technical infrastructural resources.
- A programme of deliberative ethics should explore the moral hazards of working with large language models and collections data guidelines, including environmental impacts, and potential technological unemployment, and their mitigation.

Anti-oppressive practice

UK collections linkage should encompass the breadth of UK cultural heritage and everyone it can speak to. It should therefore embrace anti-oppressive practice as a core guiding principle.

We recommend:

- Addressing gaps and biases (otherwise ‘positionality’) in cultural heritage collections data and embedding details of origin within the collections metadata
- Discussion of racism, whiteness, and intersectionality should be integrated into the working practices of all contributors to linkage.
- Understanding and addressing unequal power structures within the heritage sector that may cause holders of smaller collections and partners to reject involvement in UK collections linkage.
- Government and its departments and agencies to direct investment towards resources and infrastructure in traditionally underrepresented or underserved institutions and communities using models that work for those communities.

Open Access Data: Data deriving from public sources should be created and retained openly accessible in public repositories, without commercial paywalls, however its creation is funded. (The terms under which, for example, both historical newspaper corpora and the Census have been privatised by collaboration with the private sector has both placed this public data behind paywalls and, significantly for our enterprise, removed it from the full interoperability that will be necessary for effective collections linkage.)

Who

People power the social machine; investment in people and skills is vital to the success of UK collections linkage. Instability of roles and insufficient resourcing militate against this. We recommend:

- **Diversity of Action:** We recommend that the creation of this infrastructure should enrol diverse heritage organisations, communities and people in creating, curating and linking collections and their data.
- **Leadership** should come from a coalition of senior figures in the heritage sector (perhaps led by NMDC), DCMS and UKRI, with IROC providing expertise.
- **Funders:** The three overlapping phases of this work (research, digitisation/datafication and long-term implementation) each require bespoke funding from appropriate sources: UKRI, DCMS (local authorities), NHLF, trusts and foundations.

Our Heritage Our Stories

Our keystone recommendation is for an improved sense of the importance of community heritage amongst decision makers and the present and future role of archives in our national story. CGDC data is precious and irreplaceable, and it needs to be recognised as such by funders, the research community and the public. At present, the community archives sector is woefully underfunded and runs on goodwill, and too often, community and local archives do not receive the funding, resources, or attention and support available to other large heritage organisations. In spite of this lack of resourcing, the achievements across the UK community heritage sector are phenomenal and when set in context with the collections of large national bodies, CGDC is genuinely transformative when it comes to our national historical narrative. We therefore recommend that as part of work on a national collection, **greater funding should be allocated to the digital ambitions of the community heritage sector**, especially in terms of ensuring its long-term sustainability.

A second fundamental recommendation draws on our research that brought together historians, linguists, computer sciences and digital humanists. There is missed potential in many major funded projects that are potentially transformative for many disciplines. We need a future digital infrastructure that integrates digital resources and conceptualises them as multipurpose and re-useable collections open to all disciplines.

Archival recommendations

- As stated above, funding for the community archives and heritage sector is extremely limited and most importantly, not sustained or consistent: and yet, these organisations deal with some of the most digitally complex, fragile, and vulnerable-to-loss archival collections in the heritage sector. There is a need for community heritage organisations to work with funders to **identify what support is needed on an ongoing (not project based) basis, and to work together on business cases with organisations and government departments that provide that support**. Funders of community heritage organisations should consider urgently the funding or a network of permanent posts with a remit to support digital activities across a regional network as a collective approach to share responsibility and expertise. This could underpin structural reviews of extant data; implementing retention, selection and disposal policies for historic archives as well as newly generated ones; networking and collaborating with other organisations to pool resources; providing training to volunteers; and engaging in contemporary collecting practices.
- CGDC is critically vulnerable, and the broader community needs to work together with common purpose to prevent the irreparable loss of CGDC content; by identifying the knowledge and resources that are required; the leadership needed to champion CGDC; and by developing a set of replicable actions throughout the digital lifecycle that **always embed long-term preservation** into the creation of digital resources.
- While greater support is urgently needed for the creation, management and long-term preservation of CGDC, there is a need for models that enable ‘meeting communities where they are at’, which are embedded in community practice and sympathetic to the digital ecosystems of community heritage, and which can be flexible to specific demands/requirements/capacities of different community groups. Top-down approaches to mandates for good practice are not widely utilised or effective.

Adopting the post-custodial model developed by OHOS addresses the need for grassroots-led archival management activities.

- Community heritage organisations contribute a great deal of value, not just in the resources they make available for education and research, but in the services they provide to communities. They are often hubs for memory activities, and by making people aware of their sense of place they can build inclusive communities. We encourage all community heritage organisations to **embed within the documentation the added value of their existence to the communities they support, and actively generate quantitative and qualitative data in consistent forms** that can be understood across different types of funders.
- Everything is a metadata problem, and if that works, things fall into place. Metadata supports community archive needs to document and describe their data to the widest audiences over the long term. Rich metadata is also essential to appropriately and sensitively present data out of context: when CGDC is shared and presented outside of its original community archive context, there is a risk that data will be included that is difficult to understand or situate, or that data taken out of context seems sensitive, inappropriate, or even offensive. If the aim is to be as inclusive as possible, and not exclude sensitive data, the question of how to present it to a user in an interface needs to be considered. Without recreating a community archive’s website, it is difficult to determine how much contextual information is required to adequately situate an item in context, and technically challenging to apply this automatically and at scale. **Community archives need access to consistent, open, and free training in cataloguing and description. Sector organisations that offer face-to-face training – Archives & Records Association (ARA), Community Archives and Heritage Group (CAGH), and TNA - should be funded to develop a consultation activity to ensure that the training they offer is consistent and appropriate**, and ideally ARA accredited as appropriate.
- Plan ahead rather than look back: once a project is complete, it is often too late to consider how the CGDC’s longevity will be safeguarded as decisions regarding technical and legal aspects have already been made and resources have already been expended. **Funding bodies need to take responsibility for forward planning of CGDC they have funded, and ensure that infrastructure and guidance is in place to support informed decisions on the structure and format as well as data collection, management and preservation strategies before any content is created.** There are three main strands that come together to help ensure effective management and preservation of digital collections. They are Technology, Management, and Resources. Without some work in all these areas, preservation of digital collections in any group or organisation won’t be possible. Ultimately, digital preservation is about making an investment in properly managing digital collections with common sense, consistency and an attention to detail. Careful planning for digital preservation will safeguard assets and avoid the need for costly intervention further down the line. In addition, documenting archival practice, and why specific approaches were used, will help anyone who needs to preserve a legacy digital collection in the future.
- **A scoping exercise should be funded by NLHF or AHRC to explore how community archives can better leverage existing digital infrastructure for community heritage**, especially local council funded records office, the UK Web Archive, National Libraries, and organisations like CAHG. These organisations should work on outreach strategies for Community Heritage.

- Post-custodial approaches to archival management are highly appropriate for CGDC. They give power and control back to the data holders and creators, and are an opportunity for liminal approaches to archive management. OHOS outputs can be used as a template for these models, **further training and support for post-custodial approaches in archives should be embedded into archival education and professional training.**
- There is an urgent need for transparent models and practices for working with GDPR in the community heritage sector. **Funding should be available for access to training and advice on GDPR for community heritage.**
- **There is an urgent need for curatorial guidance to be developed on working with multilingual and multidialectal content** – asking community archives to ‘translate’ dialect terms can be disrespectful and erases the lived experience of archives and local expertise. This is particularly acute in areas (generally areas with significant working-class populations) where the use of local dialect is seen as ‘slang’ or is otherwise denigrated by staff from official organisations. Linguists have expertise in this area to support archival practitioners, while archives have rich and detailed experience of local situated knowledge to exchange with linguists who have a need for contextual data for dialects. There are therefore rich cross-exchange potentials here for the benefit of communities.
- There is no national registry or catalogue of CGDC. Manage Your Collections provides access to information about a large number of collections and collecting organisations, but does not contain information about digital items. An archival equivalent of the Museum Data Service could address this gap. **CGDC needs “a place on the map”.**

Recommendations for researchers working with CGDC materials

- **Clearer models and processes for rights management should be developed, maintained, and shared.** AHRC and national bodies with responsibility for training and the archival sector should put in place an upskilling programme for community archives on copyright regulations.
- **There is an urgent need for transparent models and practices for working with GDPR in the community heritage sector,** for both researchers and heritage staff, and for better support in developing data sharing models/agreements.
- **Researchers should integrate and document ethical considerations into every stage of the research process when working with CGDC,** and reflect on the potential harm and benefits their work may bring. It is vital to engage with stakeholders, particularly those whose work and identities are represented in CGDC, to understand their perspectives and concerns. While it may not always be necessary to seek informed consent for the use of CGDC, researchers should always consider the wishes of the individuals involved in the creation and representation of the content. For university-based researchers, there is an additional layer of responsibility. They must ensure their research adheres to institutional ethical frameworks, which may require formal peer ethical review before using CGDC materials. In this way, the guidance calls for a thoughtful, multifaceted approach to using these valuable resources, balancing legal requirements, ethical considerations, and institutional policies.
- Community heritage should be encouraged to **add descriptions of access restrictions as part of the metadata.**

Technical recommendations

- Data models for CGDC can be simple and layered: **minimal metadata is often sufficient** to make CGDC findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (**FAIR**). However, as many entities as possible should be included in documentation, if necessary in the keywords field of a metadata record, to facilitate rich entity linking and search. These entities can be added and validated by curators and/or AI.
- Wherever possible, **open formats/standards** should be used for AI/Machine Learning approaches, and any tools or outputs should be made accessible with accompanying documentation and, if possible, training materials.
- **Cross-council development work should be funded** to generate more sophisticated AI tools that can detect and handle personal data in diverse and non-standard formats, with multidialectal CGDC being a particularly fruitful testbed for complex humanities data.
- Technical solutions for CGDC should **develop more frameworks for privacy-first design**, with it being imperative that automated systems integrate tools to identify and manage personal data, ensuring compliance with regulations including GDPR. As archives increasingly contribute data from the 20th and 21st centuries, giving essential context to recent local and national challenges, addressing these privacy concerns will be crucial to maintaining trust and inclusivity and gaining access to this rich data.
- Any national collection for CGDC needs to **establish standards for processes to maintain and re-ingest data over time**, accommodating the fact that community heritage organisations update their collections and data as resources allow, meaning that more content is added, and new descriptions are created. Processes will need to be established to maintain up-to-date versions with version tracking and to enable incremental updates rather than full re-uploads in order to maintain links to enriched data already uploaded. This will also ensure compliance with GDPR by preventing the publication of personal data that a community archive has removed from their dataset since the data was aggregated. Keeping abreast of data changes over time and at scale in an automated fashion is a significant but worthwhile challenge.
- Using open-access, widely-used content (such as Wikidata) as the basis for Relation Extraction shows that there is a need for **better use of existing ontologies, authority data, and catalogue data** for the use of AI validation of cultural heritage metadata. A rich ecosystem of data exists that could be re-purposed into large language models for CGDC and related heritage content.
- To enable users to have direct access to the digital objects described in the aggregated metadata, the use of unique URIs to digital objects and their associated metadata items online should be encouraged by **funding a national URI service free at the point of use**. Beyond this, national organisations carrying out aggregation of heritage data at scale as part of a national collection should review their existing technical architecture and systems for adaptation to data to be aggregated. It is always more sustainable to work with existing, tested and robust infrastructure rather than building bespoke solutions. Digital humanities researchers contributing their expertise to a national collection should become more aware of the existing landscape of technical investment, and explore its applicability to the affordances of digital innovation around linking and discovery.

Structural/systemic recommendations

- **A radical rethink of the funding environment for digital infrastructure for digital heritage is essential.** Existing support for CGDC development and preservation varies broadly in longevity and depth and lacks overall cohesion; projects are almost always funded on a short-term basis without consideration of sustainability requirements for the long-term preservation of and access to the digital outputs they generate. Funders also have generally moved away from small grants, which can be transformative for individual archives, due to the administration cost of each grant. The UK infrastructure for community heritage therefore lacks sustainable, permanent specialist staff contracts; longer-term budget security and funding; clear and consistent advice from experts, including standardised best practice guidelines; and clearer structure and strategy across the organisations. **Funding put in place for community archives should incorporate considerations of how this data can become part of a national collection.**
- **Across the UK, there is a need for strengthened local and national structure-building for community heritage, and more powerful voices to advocate for what is needed** to ensure the required support, time and resourcing are identified and provided, and that existing and identified skills gaps in digital data are addressed across the community heritage sector.
- **A UK data infrastructure that supports the preservation, use and re-use of CGDC is urgently required.** This includes a shared and easily accessible digital repository for digital outputs of community heritage, a searchable access point for local assets, and a methods and tools interface for creative and research use of the data.
- A national collection requires the facilitation of deep collaboration between large national bodies (including IROs), sector bodies which are not research organisations, and universities. Work in this area requires incorporating at a deep and structural level an understanding of what these organisations can contribute in terms of complementary expertise and what their own local drivers and institutional priorities are. Cultural work should be done to scope the nature of these bodies as collaborators in research in order to **build workable future frameworks for fruitful large-scale collaboration.** This includes an appraisal of the underpinning legal and operational frameworks, for example those under which HEIs and civil service organisations are allowed to process and publish data.
- **Funders should provide frameworks for funding collaborations with small organisations that may be self-organising and volunteer-led over long timescales,** working in ways that may not be consistent with the timeframes and requirements of UKRI and nationally funded projects (for example, community organisations reliant on volunteer labour have to work in modular, seasonal, and incremental ways).
- **There is a need for explicitly funded local and national networks working alongside strategic and targeted funded initiatives to ensure proper futureproofing of critically endangered CGDC across the UK, in the form of a national network of practice in CGDC.** A joined-up strategy and vision needs to be set out to ensure the correct contacts and connections are made between local groups and established institutions, and it is imperative that the specifics, structures, and contingencies of the community heritage context are considered and embedded in this strategy. Additional support is required across the sector to enable a joined-up strategic approach that will encourage stable, long-term funding, with facilitated training courses and pooled organisational resources. The strategy

must ensure a diverse range of voices, communities and stories are represented in the CGDC which is preserved for future generations, and sensitivity around the collecting and representation of material which may be traumatic or contested.

Recommendations for future projects

Further recommendations have been developed by OHOS about the ways that large, interdisciplinary projects that are infrastructural in nature should be developed and funded.

- The start-up time for multi-disciplinary, multi partner and pan-institutional projects is significant. Space for this should be factored into the design of future funding schemes, with **a fully funded preparation phase of at least three months to provide investigators and project managers the space to establish necessary legal and infrastructural groundwork, including hiring project staff.** In addition, complex and multi-partner projects can face epistemological differences from the start and so we recommend projects and funding schemes hold early, dedicated workshops addressing this issue. This startup phase should also address questions of data sharing and integration from ethical and rights perspective, and the legal basis for data sharing, data processing, and data controlling. **Legal time frames and iteration need to be factored into every project that shares data across organisations.**
- Even a large-scale project will by necessity have only a small team of people working on it at each organisation, meaning that projects can themselves become silos, and gatekeeping can occur. **All team members and partners should be encouraged to talk to anyone in their institution they find might be interesting or useful,** and do the same in return, early in the project life cycle.
- It is important to always **be blunt and honest with your funder** especially if there are problems on a project. OHOS had an excellent funder, but the organisation of the wider programme could have benefitted from, and would have welcomed, feedback about what the projects needed. It is important to remember that funders learn from every project they fund.
- Failures on projects tell us just as much about successes. **Projects in the arts and humanities should be encouraged to write about failure, blog about failure, reward where people talk about failure in formal reports, and celebrate negative results.** Digital humanities is a field reaching maturity, we must celebrate that failure means our colleagues aimed high and ambitiously, and conversely that consistent success is a marker of a project aiming for the easy middle ground.

Sloane Lab

The work of building digital heritage platforms, infrastructures and resources should be understood as a techno-participatory encounter. This work requires technical expertise and ongoing, participatory research with diverse audiences, project partners, and the wider heritage sector to execute a digital cultural heritage participatory research paradigm and methodology that accommodates a plurality of perspectives and voices and does not limit publics to interacting with the national collection as curators, librarians, archivists, computer scientists and to how others have modelled it in existing platforms.

The experimental nature of the Towards a National Collection programme means that the use of participatory and co-design methodologies can risk becoming extractive in a time limited project such as Sloane Lab, an issue addressed by Towards a National Collection at a late stage in the programme (Rutherford et al. 2024). Within this wider context of the programme structure and funding, ensuring that symbiotic, co-operative and lasting relationships were formed with participants was a key challenge faced by the Sloane Lab team and one that should be a key consideration of future digital heritage funding programmes.

The project Fellowship scheme brought new voices and expertise into the Sloane Lab. Nevertheless, the elaboration, advertising, interviewing and supervisory work entailed in the Fellowship programme for Sloane Lab staff was substantial and largely invisible. Realistic resourcing of such initiatives should be a key consideration of future digital heritage funding programmes.

Digital technology can play a crucial role in delivering automated and augmented ways of bringing together collections in museums, galleries, libraries, and archives, of mending the broken links between the past and present of the UK's founding collection in the catalogues of the British Museum, Natural History Museum, and the British Library. Yet this work necessarily involves a substantial investment of staff time, in otherwise invisible activities like data cleaning, checking and resolution. Due consideration of this is crucial in future digital cultural heritage projects.

Discussions about digital infrastructure development often lay great emphasis on questions and problems that are technical and legal in nature. Important as technical and legal matters are, more latent, yet potent challenges exist too. Though less discussed in the literature, collecting and heritage organisations' capacity to participate in digital infrastructures is dependent on a complex interplay of resource ontology and allocation across the heritage sector and within collecting and heritage organisations, including divergent traditions of collection description and disciplinary idiosyncrasies. Accordingly, we call for better social-cultural and trans-sectoral (collecting and heritage organisations, universities and technological providers) understandings of collection data infrastructure development.

Sloane Lab sought to facilitate richer, more critical understandings of the origins and development of museum collections by devising computational and conceptual approaches to detecting and exposing often-hidden processes like colonialism, empire and slavery that have shaped collections and their classifications. A five-year period of funding would have enabled deeper analysis and research of the huge wealth of data that the project managed to mobilise and ingest into the Knowledge Base in a three year time frame

Sloane Lab has been built on a trans-sectoral and extramural partnership, across universities, museums libraries and a range of communities. It has required a range of expertise, knowledge and interest that goes far beyond what one individual, disciplinary area or institution can possess. Whilst funding delivered by schemes like Towards a National Collection is crucial to facilitate cross-sector research, the Sloane Lab project

came about due to long standing, trans-sectoral partnerships that far preceded Towards a National Collection. If Sloane Lab has shown that people are just as crucial as technology in the work of imagining how digital platforms that can be used, tell new stories about what can be rediscovered, and reimagined, by linking collections, then this should not be understood as extending to the active research process only. Ongoing ways for universities, heritage institutions, interested and expert individuals and communities to maintain their partnerships outside of short-term Towards a National Collection-like programmes and funding schemes are necessary and require support from funders.

Transforming Collections

The Towards a National Collection conference held on 26 April 2023 at the British Museum highlighted institutional impulses towards standardisation, diversification and a sense of opportunity and urgency around the potential for the cumulative efforts and learnings of 30 years of investment into the digitisation of collections so far, to converge through the TaNC programme and consolidate into a digital strategy for dissolving barriers, broadening access, knowledge and representation. There was also a welcome questioning of ‘what a true digital landscape really means’, a call to ‘truly unlock potential’ and for ‘honest[y] about challenges’.

Sessions structured around the themes of ‘Innovation’, ‘Inclusion’ and ‘Collaboration’ belied their mutual entanglement and dependency as necessary conditions for meaningful engagement and world-changing research, that might not only critically challenge understandings of what the ‘challenges’ are, but also open up and transform understandings of what a ‘national collection’ might be or become. For *Transforming Collections*, inclusive practices have been fundamental to genuine collaboration and innovation in research that might afford or generate alternative world views and ‘worldings’.⁶⁷ The pervasive simplistic and binaristic characterisation of stakeholders as ‘researchers and communities’, ‘collections and audiences’, or ‘institutions and individuals’ (misrepresented, marginalised or excluded historically and in the present), or the recognition of excluded subjects after the fact, fails to address deeply embedded structural power differentials. ‘Barriers’ are often invoked as a technological challenge to be addressed in the domain of ‘digital innovation’, while social and cultural barriers are more likely to be considered at the ‘end point’ of project delivery and dissemination, notionally addressed through a belated ‘bringing in’ of so-called ‘hard to reach’ audiences. So-called ‘collaboration’ can disguise extractive and instrumentalising practices, unless frameworks and mechanisms for reflexivity, accountability, attribution are embedded, and the ways and processes by which lines between choices, decisions, actions and consequences are drawn are also made transparent.

There is also, perhaps, a latent tendency to understand ‘true’ in this context as ‘pure’, as in a ‘pure digital landscape’. Rather than seeing the ‘digital landscape’ as an idealised future space to be ‘cleaned up’ and removed from the analogue, we might lean into the empowering notion of ‘honesty’ (if it is reciprocated and sustained) – to embrace the messy realities, complexities and contradictions of the digital and analogue artefacts and collections in the past, present and future, as inhabiting a shared and contested continuum. We might then approach the inconsistencies and gaps between analogue and digital records not as problems to be resolved and closed, but as opportunities to necessarily expose and explore the partiality of ‘truths’ and knowledges from privileged perspectives, and how these are constructed and perpetuated through particular periods, contexts and practices. This includes the truths of the hidden labour, entangled exploitations and ecological impacts powerfully demonstrated by the *Anatomy of an AI System*, cited by international guest speaker and *Ars Electronica* CTO, Horst Hörtner (a map of human labour, data and

⁶⁷ Gayatri Chakravorty Spivak, ‘The Rani of Sirmur: An Essay in Reading the Archives’, *History and Theory* 24, no.3, October 1985, pp.247–72.

planetary resources using the example of Amazon Echo to show the countless components and factors behind the production of *artificial intelligence systems*⁶⁸). If ‘standardisation’ does not enable heterogeneities, differences and gaps and hidden relations to remain or become visible, it risks replicating existing harms.

Another international guest, Setareh Noorani, spoke eloquently to the collective collaborative work at the Nieuwe Instituut on ‘collecting otherwise’, articulating the urgency of committing to collective care and accountability while testing modes of activation, contestation, and negotiation, to invigorate relations with archives and collections. Questions of heritage necessarily prompt questions of provenance, ownership, restitution and reparation too. As such, in the process of ‘unlocking potential’ for greater connectivity and accessibility, we must also ensure greater care in respecting the rights of the living, deceased, and their ancestors, identified and otherwise, whose objects have been variously ‘gifted’, donated or dubiously acquired. Attention to records and rights necessitates time and human-centred care, to rethink, enact, re-dress, revisit, and human-scale resistance to uncritical acceleration at scale. Here, ‘standardisation’, should refer to the standard embedding of ethical considerations, including the Nieuwe Instituut’s notion of an ‘archival care rider’, which might be expanded into an ‘archival and collections care rider.’

The systemic and structural work of change cannot be imagined, delivered or sustained without centring and sustaining the humans historically decentred yet deeply implicated in this work. Inclusive, equitable and ethical collaborative practices must underpin and drive inclusive innovation in research. This includes acknowledging and mitigating programme pressures on project set up and recruitment timelines, their cumulative negative impacts on the project team and research capacity, and the importance of allocating strategic follow-on funding to mitigate the potential erosion of research outcomes and relationships. As we close the *Transforming Collections* project, our recommendations for consolidating the work of the project and the wider TaNC programme, to maximise the potential impacts of the five Discovery Projects, are set out below.

We recommend that future funding criteria should require projects to:

1. **Recruit a diverse, inclusive and representative research team** with lived personal and professional experiences relevant to the wider questions, aims, objectives and intended audiences and beneficiaries of the project.
2. **Engage diverse and directly implicated stakeholders as early as possible** in bid development, project conceptualisation, and iterative design and delivery stages, including researchers, artists, estates and archival donors.
3. **Value and embed practice-led or practice-based research and close interdisciplinary collaboration** to help understand research enquiries and impacts.
4. **Value and embed active engagement with the ethics and ethical implications** of the research in principle and in practice.

⁶⁸ Kate Crawford and Vladan Joler, ‘Anatomy of an AI System’, 2018, <https://anatomyof.ai/>.

We recommend strategic investment in:

5. Further resource to **deepen and extend critical engagement and evaluation** activities beyond the end of the funded three-year period. This would enable the triangulation and **underpinning of heritage information as data, and human/digital interactions, with ethical practice**, e.g. by examining approaches to language across all Discovery Projects.
6. Further resource for an extended programme to **roll-out durational testing** of our **adaptable, interactive ML tools** designed to work with existing infrastructures. This would enable sustained engagement to gather **feedback over time** from **cross-partner, cross-project, cross-sector and cross-disciplinary** and **international** stakeholders.
7. **Flexible interactive tools to enhance existing and future infrastructures with critical prompts and reflexive valves**. This is needed to encourage the **rethinking** of habitual formulations, hierarchies, values and vocabularies, and enable **dynamic categorisations** or tags to be created and refined by users, **'delinking and relinking' data** to reflect back the users' choices, surfacing biases as well as unexpected relations.
8. **Long-term cataloguing** work across project and programme partnerships informed by researchers' subject specialisms and interests, using the interactive ML application as a critical analytical tool. This would enrich digital records by making more **transparent** the choices of authors, **surfacing connections, contexts and absences**.
9. **Conserving analogue archives** and collection materials recognising their **integral importance in relation to digital records**. Not to situate the digital in hierarchical opposition or superior progressive relation to the analogue but rather to **make explicit the gaps, discrepancies and omissions** across digital and analogue data, as part of the holistic and **inevitably incomplete record**.

Unpath'd Waters

Recommendations for Developing a UK Digital Collection

Collections Development

The following recommendations are provided by way of support to those wider policy recommendations issued through the TaNC programme in November 2024⁶⁹.

- **Discovering collections:** The scoping of any follow-on activity from TaNC should be clear about the degree to which focus is placed on metadata or rich datasets. Both are needed to unleash the potential of a true national collection and a clear criterion-based strategy will be needed.
- **Authority and control:** The extent to and circumstances in which authority files and controlled vocabularies should be imposed is a complex ethical and technical issue relating to potential end-use and end-users of collections. A strategic approach will be needed to ensure a balance for different kinds of collections. This will have international implications.
- **Artificial Intelligence:** Given the rapidly expanding capabilities of AI, the need for tracking of how outputs and labels have been created will be essential, especially for collections used for legislative or strategic management purposes.
- **Dynamic data:** Some collections are designed to grow and change (e.g. national inventories). Others are static (e.g. a historical collection of objects). Efforts to enhance the former will require workflows that allow enhanced data to feed back into original repositories and be recognised there.
- **Connectivity and accessibility:** Formatting of new, future collections will be crucial in ensuring that the full range of abilities of users (for example the visually impaired) is built-in at the outset. This has significant implications.
- **Ethics:** related to connectivity, we recommend that human and more-than-human centred design is made a core component of any future national collection, at an infrastructure as well as collection level.
- **Inherent issues in collections:** collections created in the past use language and approaches rooted in that past. Linking such collections may surface difficult and inappropriate language and consistent approaches to this risk are required.

Digitisation of Analogue Collections

As part of our Analogue to Digital Connector work we developed an initial consideration of how to prioritise the digitisation of analogue collections. We make two assumptions in proposing this. The first is that the fundamental value in digitally unlocking our collections to grow audiences, empower research, and drive

⁶⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13838916>

economic growth is a given. Prioritisation is therefore not a simply binary ‘do’ or ‘don’t do’. Instead, it is ‘do first’ or ‘do later’. The second is that individual organisations will continue to digitise using their own criteria: the prioritisation approach we suggest is complementary, supporting funding organisations who have a choice in which collection(s) to address next.

We recommend that the TaNC programme offers some basic advice to all funders and supporters of digitisation of collections.

This advice should draw from the criteria that were identified at the expert symposium, but also from the range of existing published criteria and approaches that are used by principal archive and collection organisations. Here we draw on the significance criteria for archives published by The National Archive⁷⁰, and also adopted for museum collections in Significance 3.0⁷¹, and on digitisation guidance published originally by Culture24⁷².

The significance of a given physical collection can be (and may well already have been) assessed against the following basic criteria:

- **Provenance:** who created, collected and has used the collection.
- **Rarity:** whether the collection is unique or unusual, and if it is a particularly fine example of a collection of its type.
- **Condition and completeness:** whether the collection is intact and in good condition, and if its condition can say anything about its history, ownership or use.
- **Historical, cultural or scientific meaning:** how the collection tells the story of particular people, groups, organisations, events, places, beliefs, or practices; whether it has special historic or cultural interest for an audience, region or community; whether and how it could be used for academic research; and whether it enriches or fills in gaps in other collections.
- **Sensory and emotional impact:** whether the collection has strong visual/sensory impact or evokes a strong personal or cultural response; and whether the language, format, technique, design or style reflect outstanding creativity or innovation.
- **Marketing and exploitability:** whether the collection could support marketing, income generation or profile-raising.

But the decision to digitise any collection which is able to demonstrate significance is a further consideration. Here it is possible to apply further tests based on our Analogue to Digital Connector work. For example:

- **Retention of faithfulness:** does digitising carry across sufficient of what makes the collection significant?
- **Removal of barriers:** does the proposal eradicate or reduce existing barriers to access (such as logistics, legal issues, etc)?

⁷⁰ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/archives-sector/grants-and-funding/records-at-risk-grants/how-to-apply/assessment-criteria/>

⁷¹ <https://collectionstrust.org.uk/resource/reviewing-significance-3-0/>

⁷² <https://digipathways.co.uk/what-should-i-digitise/>

- **Preservation:** does digitising help to secure fragile or vulnerable collections for the future?

More work would be required to establish how helpful this recommendation is, but we are convinced that would be effort well spent.

Programme Infrastructure

These recommendations may assist in structuring future investment opportunities.

- **Research Council funding equity.** The very positive innovation seen in the TaNC programme of including Collaborating Organisations as part of the research ecology created many benefits to Unpath'd Waters. However, the stance taken on their funding created difficulties where they, several being small-scale charities, could not claim overhead costs. This seems unfair and unnecessary and should be reviewed.
- **Supporting smaller organisations to become FAIR.** While national heritage bodies involved in the Unpath'd Waters consortium had a good understanding of FAIR and had implemented many of the principles, partners representing smaller organisations or projects within academic departments had more of a learning curve. Most were able to work through the process with much of the data they had hoped to include, which resulted in both heightened awareness of what implementing FAIR Principles actually entails, and the importance of FAIRness on their practices and workflows going forward, and this should be supported in any move towards a UK digital collection.
- **Develop programme-level values.** Drawing on our work on values-led project development and evaluation, we suggest that funders, whilst not prescribing values or enforcing them upon new projects, should undertake their own values setting process in order to fully understand the logistical commitment here and to set a precedent for subsequent organisational behaviours.
- **Training support.** Funders should be made aware of any appetite for training required in novel areas for which no consistent track record has yet been developed, which they then could support as part of any project.
- **Climate impact and carbon footprint.** Leadership, shared aims, and guidance should be provided by funders on how project teams can reduce carbon footprints from the outset of their project. Funders, in fact, should have their own clear commitments.

Recommendations for Marine and Maritime Collections

The National Records

A rich set of interchanges between those responsible for managing national inventories was provoked by the Unpath'd Waters project. This led to some broad recommendations which, if adopted, will help improve all four home nation inventories. These are:

Improving the collections

- Provide persistent identifiers (PIIDs) to physical objects and documentary records of wrecks so as to allow for a vessel name to be allocated and reallocated across physical entities as information changes.
- Resolve default labelling. Where something is not known it should be labelled as such.
- Resolve false specificity in precision and accuracy in wreck location reporting.
- Recording depth/vertical extent of sites and wrecks in a consistent manner⁷³
- Develop ways of spatially characterising significant marine landscape features (e.g. priority areas derived from Unpath'd Waters Simulation, coastal and intertidal peat data, and others) to allow their incorporation into management systems.
- Enhancement of event records (investigations, surveys, excavations and so on), and a closer relationship with the Archaeology Data Service's OASIS flowline which captures metadata on these events.
- Developing and publication of the spatial component, including spatial extents where known, of the Events module to better reflect the temporal history of wreck locations.
- Developing ship's biographies to more fully document the lifecycle of vessels from commissioning, construction and naming, through journeys to loss in addition to the rediscovery and recording of wreck sites.
- Using connected collections to identify environmental hazards of historic wrecks in marine inventories.
- Creation of linkages to historical collections (e.g. LRHEC or RNLI), allowing for a much richer and more compelling understanding of the stories of individual ships and people.

Improving data flows

- Closer exchange of information with the Admiralty's Centre for Seabed Mapping; the Wrecks Section of the UK Hydrographic Office; the Civil Hydrography programme; to ensure that newly discovered features on the seabed are incorporated into the record quickly.
- Improving information ingest and publication from large area surveys and targeted projects to ensure better decision making and stewardship of the historic environment by stakeholders from archaeologists to the offshore renewables industry.
- Enhancing the flowline of information with the commercial archaeology sector to improve how information from development-led work is captured within the record.
- Streamline data flows from citizen science data producers into the national inventories.

Equitable handling of citizen science

⁷³ For example, https://medin.org.uk/sites/medin/files/documents/MEDIN_Schema_Documentation_3_1_2_brief.pdf

- Give due acknowledgement in outputs to the origin of data sources created by ‘citizen science’ programmes, permitting each to be ‘surfaced’ as separate collection groups.

Raising awareness

- Work with relevant governmental bodies on matters of mutual interest with regard to survey and spatial data management planning.
- Raising public awareness of marine heritage assets, in partnership with other key sector stakeholders (e.g. national museums, the higher education sector, relevant Non-Governmental Organisations), through research, virtual access, archive collections and educational and outreach activities.

Recommendations for Developing Values-led Projects

Values offer (a qualitative form of) self and group accountability, which - when applied critically - lead to greater efficiencies and collaboration within the team, greater innovation, and ultimately then to greater value-for-money and less wastage (of time and money). We make a number of recommendations based on our work:

Improving Collaborations Through Values

- **Develop a project-wide and living values framework.** There are significant cross-project benefits to be realised in proper preparation and implementation across collaborations, especially where different cultures of research or practice exist.
- **Embed values frameworks by developing value advocates.** Leads and PIs should aim to establish a team structure that nurtures value advocates across the project (not centred only in one work package) who regularly encourage or nurture values-rich conversations. Ringfencing time, money and expertise to create such advocacy roles would allow values leadership to be better distributed across the consortium, with advocates able to advise work packages more closely on values methodologies.
- **Define values early.** It is imperative that the project defines values as early in the process as possible in order for colleagues to begin to plan their outputs in accordance with them. Use open values rather than closed (tick-box) values and consider audience-centring them.
- **Ensure the framework is not unwieldy and overly bureaucratic.** Reporting to numerous values measures is cumbersome and drains limited capacity, leading to a lack of understanding of required or desirable values-led practices.
- **Recognise and account for programmatic and institutional operations which may sit in conflict with values.** Values can easily and regularly be undermined by the everyday operational practices and policies of institutional partners. Hurdles in sharing technology or images, conflicting or exclusionary intellectual property, proformas that are inaccessible to people with visual impairments using screen readers; financial systems that will not allow simple forms of compensation via voucher, are all examples of barriers which can be removed early in any project.

- **Simplify values recall.** Values, associated action statements, and measures could be hard to remember. Ways of presenting the values as logos or graphics may be useful as shorthand. However, such visuals must be simply fashioned (to promote changeability) and designed with accessibility in mind.
- **Hold teams to account.** Values Advocates can help to mitigate negative or unconstructive behaviours which contradict the values, focus on positive reinforcement of the values, and identify persistent problems with project leads where escalation is needed. Audience-focused training across teams (e.g. in outreach or evaluation) may also help to embed more values-led practices.
- **Adopt other organisational or community values.** More work is required in considering how external values, held by our target audiences and external partners, could be integrated into our Values Framework. Early discussions with external partners to gain an understanding of their values, and how they hold themselves accountable to these could act as an ‘icebreaker’ introduction.

Shaping Public Engagement Evaluation through Values

Similarly, our work on values-led evaluation threw up some very useful recommendations for future projects considering this approach in the context of public events, trials or exhibitions.

- **Suites of simple guidelines.** Prepare resources at an early stage:
 - specific guidance around the audiences where the project has the least experience.
 - simple checklist type does and don'ts.
 - logos and infographics to add to PowerPoint slides on evaluation/measuring of our objectives.
 - impact measurement template.
 - evaluation tools.
 - link to relevant toolkits.
- **Training of team members in audience evaluation.** This will help to ensure more consistent administration of evaluation activities and better-quality data collection.
- **Smoothing the path for data-sharing.** GDPR and ethics also negatively impact on data sharing across work packages. Programme-level support is necessary in ensuring multi-institution projects can move data between partners to perform rigorous analysis.
- **Planning technological requirements.** The touring exhibition, bus and Voyager relied significantly on technology and Wi-Fi connectivity, but there were often issues with electrical links and internet which affected the visitor experience.
- **Delegate evaluation activities locally.** Exhibitions to be evaluated must have staff dedicated to conduct evaluation. Staffing must come from within museum teams in order to react quickly, to reduce carbon consumption and to offer context that only a local member of the institution can provide.

- **Experiment with ‘audience-centred’ evaluation methods.** Research investment must be directed towards evaluation methodologies themselves, rather than investing in other forms of innovation and carrying on with evaluative approaches we know both to be ineffective and to contravene our own values.
- **Bring research outputs directly to different audiences** (beyond existing heritage institutions). To truly reach out to new audiences and those who do not usually engage in heritage, the project needs to be more adventurous in its choice of exhibition locations. Examples of more diverse visitor spaces with larger footfall could be roadside service stations, supermarket car parks or transport terminals, amongst many other options.

Recommendations for Managing Large Consortia

There were several lessons learned which may help planning future consortia of this kind.

- The impact of recruitment delays should not be underestimated. It can’t be helped if programme management staff move on but developing a backup strategy and ensuring ‘desk instructions’ are available will help in transitional periods.
- Recruitment delays within delivery teams also caused unsurprising knock-on impacts to the programme. While we managed this with a level of flexibility within the programme as a whole, there are limits to how far that can help. One strategy for replacement of staff was to recruit multiple short-term PDRA positions to support Co-Investigators, each with slightly different skill-sets. This made it easier to match the total skill requirements, rather than waiting an extended time for one individual who could cover every base. This strategy also saw an increase in Early Career Researcher involvement in the project.
- We did not calculate the capacity required for meeting times both within the project and beyond it (joining TaNC programme meetings for example). This was a capacity issue both in real terms (not quite enough Co-I time for example), seasonal terms (where Co-Is or Collaborating Organisation staff were committed to fieldwork, teaching or commercial work outside the project), and in terms of programming (where critical path tasks were required to be completed at the time of the meetings).
- It might be possible for UKRI to develop financial reporting templates which could be used to match the requirements of Final Expenditure Statements. That way, the in-flight financial reporting would more closely match the end requirements of any given project.
- Full-time administrative support should be costed when consortia are above a certain size.

ⁱ <https://openglam.org/> and <https://collectionsasdata.github.io/>

ⁱⁱ Anon, ‘About | FreeCEN’.

ⁱⁱⁱ Shadbolt et al., *The Theory and Practice of Social Machines*.